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Evaluation on Annotations of Music Emotion Dataset

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Abstract

Music emotion recognition is an important part of music information research. However, because emotion is highly personal and subjective, and it is difficult to quantify, it usually cannot be described accurately. Therefore, it is always difficult to collect high-quality annotations on music emotion studies. Moreover, because the emotion in a song or a music piece may change over time as it plays, its dynamic property also makes it hard to annotate the emotion when listening to music. What's more, for research purposes, we need to clarify the distinction between perceived emotions and induced emotions. But people without professional training can easily get confused about the two concepts. These factors make it difficult for us to obtain neutral and objective annotations on music emotion. In 2017, Aljanaki et al. released a dataset MediaEval Database for Emotional Analysis in Music (DEAM), which consists of royalty-free music, emotion-related music feature-sets, and annotation from scrupulous and well-trained annotators. The data in DEAM was collected gradually between 2013 and 2015. Every year, the compiler would organize a benchmark task in the MediaEval community to evaluate the feature-sets and the predicting models. In this work, we focus on the annotation data. Specifically, to apply machine-learning algorithms to select annotations that are closer to each other. Then verify if these more similar annotations can improve the accuracy in music emotion predicting. In the end, we will compare the performance of different selecting methods.

Keywords: Music Emotion Recognition; DEAM Dataset; Annotation; Clustering.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Research Motivation

Music, like language and writing, is a form of expression and communication that has been passed down through generations and continues to be used today. But rather than language and writing, the rise and fall of melodies and the changes of rhythm in music can help us regulate our emotions. When we are restless, soft music can calm us down. when we are feeling down, powerful music can instantly revive us. when we toss and turn, soothing music can relax our nerves and help us quickly drift into sleep. In [59], Lamere conducted a study on social tagging on Last.fm (<http://www.last.fm/>). The result shows that emotion is the third most common tag assigned by users, just following genre and locale. Studies on cross-cultural music show that in addition to language and cultural adaptation, there may also be universal psychological and emotional signals in music [70, 14, 40]. That is, emotions in music can transcend language and cultural differences and be communicated across people from different backgrounds. The study of music emotion recognition (MER) aims to extract features that are relevant to emotion from audio content-based analysis, which is a relatively new but important aspect of music information research (MIR). By analyzing the emotions in music, we can put it into use for a variety of purposes. For instance, in the psychological field to improve people's work efficiency, in commercial intention to attract users or improve

user's experiences, mood regulation, etc.

With the rapid development of digital technology and the internet since the end of last century, musical resources have exploded. Besides categorizing music by age, genre, language, region, etc, people also want to classify music by the emotions in music to satisfy the need for music in different moods. But unlike common search or retrieval categories, which are easy to get a "correct" or commonly agreed-on answer [56], emotion is highly subjective and difficult to quantify.

One of the biggest limitations in the study of MER is the lack of high-quality annotations. Emotions are generated subconsciously and influenced by many factors. Although almost every one of us is seeking some emotional resonances when listening to music, we can barely describe the "emotion" accurately. Unlike tags of the artist (genres, gender, nationality, etc) or the song (language for example), the tag of emotion in a piece of certain music makes it hard to reach an agreement. In addition, annotating with emotional labels is burdensome.

Another factor that affects annotation quality is that it is normally difficult for listeners to understand and figure out the difference between perceived emotions and induced emotions in music. Perceived emotions are the emotions expressed by the music with some music properties (such as key, mode, tempo, etc), while induced emotions are those aroused by the music within the listener when they are listening. For example, a song with a slow tempo, bright timbre and poetic lyrics is often considered to express calmness. But if a person once listened to this song in a nervous state, for example, cannot work out questions in an important exam, he/she will probably feel anxious and panic when listening to this song again.

Copyright is also an obstacle to the research of MER. Due to audio copyright restrictions, the audios cannot be redistributed by researchers, and the data sets used in studies are hardly made public and reused in other studies [11]. Although there are some data sets like Creative Commons used to collect music that is distributed for free under a license, they usually don't have many tags and annotations, which makes them less well-known.

Unlike other static art works, music is dynamic. The emotion in a song or music piece may change over time. On music websites, each song usually has only 1 tag in every aspect, which is not enough for emotion. So, how to annotate the emotion features in a music work precisely over time is also a problem to be solved.

In 2017, Aljanaki et al. released a dataset *MediaEval Database for Emotional Analysis of Music* (DEAM) [11]. The dataset basically solves the problems mentioned above. It contains 1744 clips and 58 full-length royalty-free songs from a variety of music genres. The annotations on the music are focused on emotion in music, both static and dynamic emotions. The emotions are annotated with a dimensional approach (see in 2.1.2), and the annotators were relatively professional in musical psychology.

In 2019, Bogdanov et al. presented the *MTG-Jamendo Dataset* [21]. It is an open dataset for music auto-tagging. The dataset contains 55609 full-length audio tracks from 3565 artists, 195 tags for *genre* (95), *instrument* (41) and *mood/theme* (59) categories, which makes it a really large dataset. Compared to DEAM, besides the annotations that correlated with emotion, the MTG-Jamendo Dataset is also concerned on general and cultural aspects. Since the music in the MTG-Jamendo Dataset is annotated by tags, the way to classify emotion is a categorical approach (see in 2.1.1).

1.2 Research Objectives

In this thesis, we are going to improve the accuracy of the dataset by “purifying” the annotation data. That is, to select similar annotations of every song, and test if the accuracy with only these “similar” annotations will be improved. What methods and algorithms to cluster similar annotations is what we consider in the work.

Then, we apply different methods or parameters in every step of the classification process, and find out the combination that could achieve the best performance. In the end, we will analyze the performance with different methods and algorithms used, and find out how these methods and algorithms impact the performance.

- 1 Impact of quantization fineness
- 2 Impact of manifold learning algorithms in clustering
- 3 Impact of clustering algorithms
- 4 Differences between cluster selection methods

1.3 Report Structure

The rest of this thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides some basic definitions and current state-of-the-art methods related to our work in Music Emotion Recognition. In Chapter 3, we detail the materials we used and the methodology of our study. Chapter 4 represents the results of our study. In the final chapter, we discuss the experimental results, elaborate on our conclusions and potential work to expand our work in this field.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

In this chapter, we will introduce previous studies and tools related to this work. Including emotion description methods in psychology, emotion-related features in music and computer tools to extract them, some widely used music-perceived emotion datasets, and machine-learning algorithms.

2.1 Emotion Description

In psychology studies, there are two main approaches to classify or recognize emotions: *categorical approach* and *dimensional approach*.

2.1.1 Categorical Approach

The idea of categorical conceptualization of emotion is that emotions are discrete and can be categorized into a few classes. For example, happy, sad, surprise, anger, and fear etc. All other secondary emotion classes can be derived from these basic emotion types [33, 82]. Moreover, these basic emotions can be found in all cultures, and are usually related to distinct patterns of physiological changes or different patterns of emotional expressions.

In 1936, Hevner conducted an experiment on expressions in music [50]. She provided a list of 66 adjectives for listeners and let them pick one(s) that they think most

Figure 1: 66 adjectives grouped in 8 classes by Hevner [50]

suit the emotions in a piece of music. Later, she arranged these 66 adjectives into 8 groups and laid these groups in a circle as shown in Fig 1. In the figure, we can see that the adjectives in each group are closely related, the meanings of adjacent groups change gradually and reach a contrast in the opposite position. In later researches, Farnsworth refined Hevner’s study and categorized the 66 adjectives into 10 groups [39], and in [88] Schubert updated them into 9 groups. In 2008, Hu et al. categorized songs into one of 5 mood clusters in an MIREX audio mood classification task [32]. No matter how many clusters the adjectives are finally grouped, this categorical approach is centered on the opinion that almost all emotions can be classified into some general categories.

2.1.2 Dimensional Approach

The dimensional approach suggests that emotions can be evaluated from several dimensions. We can describe an emotion from different perspectives. For example, how intense or weak, how positive or negative, the object of emotion is oneself or others, etc. Then, combine these descriptions together like a high-dimensional space

to represent an emotion in an all-round way.

The most noted and widely used dimensional approach is the 2-dimensional *Valence-Arousal* (V-A) space (Fig 2). In V-A space, emotions are depicted in a 2-dimensional plane, which is composed of independent axes of arousal (intensity or energy), ranging high-to-low, and valence (the level of positive), ranging positive-to-negative [86].

Figure 2: The Valence-Arousal space, with some emotions labeled by Russell [86]

One of the best advantages of the V-A model is that it provides a simple but efficient way to combine emotions from physiological perspective, which is arousal, and psychological perspective, which is valence. On the model, we can compare the “value” directly on these two standard and important dimensions.

Some criticisms argue that in some circumstances the V-A model can not distinguish some essential psychological distinctions clearly. For example, anger and fear are both accompanied with high arousal and negative emotions. Corresponding to the V-A plane, these two emotions are very close to each other, both in the second quadrant represents high arousal and negative valence. However, anger and fear are very different in terms of psychology. In other words, V-A model blurs some aspects of emotion process [105]. To overcome this drawback, some researchers expanded this approach to a 3-dimensional space with potency, ranging dominant-submissive,

Figure 3: Hevner's classification in the V-A space

as the third dimension [16]. However, the third dimension is somehow subject to speculation and disagreement. What's more, a 3D space is more difficult to perform than a 2D plane. So the V-A model is still dominant in emotion annotation work.

In fact, if we adjust the positions of every emotion label in Fig 1 slightly while keeping their relative positions unchanged, we can easily find that these gradually changed model basically matches the V-A space by rotating the adjectives clockwise on the origin. (Fig 3). This can be explained by how these two approaches developed. In the categorical approach, because the meaning changes gradually among groups, the closer the group, the closer the meaning. When two groups are located in the opposite position, the meanings they represent reach a contrast. In the dimensional approach, positions close to each other on the V-A space indicate their arousal and valence are similar, which means the emotions they show are similar. On a 2-dimensional plane, any two points that are symmetrical about the origin represent opposite values. It is also true in the V-A space. For each pair of origin-symmetric points, the emotions they represent are completely opposite.

2.2 Emotionally-Relevant Features

People’s speaking voice would change when their moods are different. For example, when angry, people often raise their voices or even “shout out” when their anger reach a high level. If someone is in a hurry, they would speak faster than usual. Music is the same. It is associated with different acoustic features when expressing or in different emotions. [49] and [84] noted that the emotion perception in music is often dependent on a combination of several sets of features but not single ones. In [105], Yang and Chen briefly classified the features that are most relevant to and commonly used in MER into 4 categories : *Energy*, *Rhythm*, *Melody* and *Timbre*. In [77], Panda et al summarized acoustic features that are widely adopted in audio analysis tools/software: *Rhythm*, *Dynamics*, *Melody*, *Harmony*, *Tonal color*, *Music form*, *Expressive techniques*, and some other experimental high-level descriptors.

Energy

The energy of a signal corresponds to its total magnitude. It represents the intensity of the music. The energy of music is closely related to its arousal. Usually, high volume, high pitch, or fast tempo would make a high energy.

In the study of emotion classification, Root-Mean-Square Energy is often used to express the energy of music signals [56]. But before the sound is accepted by people’s brains, ears have performed a series of complex transformations on the original audio signal, people’s sense of loudness is related to a bunch of factors. For example, if the frequency of sound waves with the same intensity is different, the loudness felt by human ears will be different. Therefore, people sometimes use “perceived” loudness like specific loudness sensation (SONE) to quantify the intensity of music [15].

Rhythm

Music is a kind of combination of sound and time. When sounds are produced (by a singer, instruments, etc.) over a period of time, a piece of music has been made [28]. The recurrence of sound and silence (notes and rests) of different lengths

is the rhythm of this music. Rhythm is shaped by meter, and has elements like tempo and beat [35]. Tempo is a key element of arousal and valence. A fast tempo often produces higher values in arousal. If the rhythm is fluent (the combination of each sound in the phrase is harmonious, the transition between phrases is coherent, and the development of melody in some certain rules,) it is usually associated with positive valence. On the contrary, a firm rhythm often leads to a negative valence [41].

In [63], Lu et al. proposed five features to describe the rhythmic features of music: rhythm strength, rhythm distinctness, rhythm regularity, average tempo, and average onset frequency. In [56], Kim et al. summarized the most common rhythm features for emotion recognition are Rhythm strength, regularity, tempo, and beat histograms.

Melody

A melody is a series of notes played sequentially which make themselves recognizable and make people remember them as a single entity [27]. Melody is a combination of rhythm and pitch. Specifically, melody is the pitch changing in some rhythm.

Early MIR researchers used pitch contour, the direction of tone change, to represent melody. In [42], Ghias et al. described the contour of the melody with relationships between pitches. They used ‘U’, ‘D’, and ‘S’ to represent the pitch fluctuation of the melody. The three letters mean up, down and same separately, but without the depiction of rhythm. Based on Ghias’s research, the duration of each note was added as a new feature vector to depict the rhythm of music. In [76], Ozcan et al. proposed an approach to extract melody from MIDI files, which could distinguish different melody channels.

Timbre

Timbre is one of the three elements of sound. Timbre means that different sounds always have different characteristics in waveform. Sound is generated by the vibration of the sounding object. When the object vibrates, it will emit a pitch. At the

same time, different parts in this object also generate compound vibrations. The sounds generated by the compound vibrations are combined into overtones. The timbre of a sound is determined by overtones.

In music, timbre encompasses a range of auditory characteristics that contribute to the musical quality of a sound. It arises from events generated by multiple sound sources that are perceptually combined or merged into a unified auditory image [67]. Timbre distinguishes different types of sound production or musical instruments. It is also called *sound quality* or *sound color* in psycho-acoustics [4].

In signal processing, timbre is determined by the shape of the waveforms. The spectral centroid is a key physical parameter that describes timber qualities. It is used to represent a spectrum and indicates the gravity center of the spectrum. [100]. The centroid in a spectral frame is defined as the average frequency weighted by amplitudes, divided by the sum of the amplitudes [75]. In the subjective perception field, the spectral centroid describes the brightness of the sound. Sounds with a darker and lower quality generally have more low-frequency content, resulting in a relatively low spectral centroid. In contrast, sounds with a brighter and more cheerful quality are concentrated in the higher frequencies, leading to a relatively higher spectral centroid.

In MIR, a commonly used timbre-related feature is Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCC). MFCC is a set of feature vectors that represents the contour (envelope) of the spectrum. The human auditory system is nonlinear. It exhibits varying sensitivity to sound waves at different frequencies. MFCC transforms a linear spectrum into a Mel-scale nonlinear spectrum based on auditory perception, and then converts it into cepstral coefficients. In the Mel frequency domain, human perception of frequency will be converted to a linear relationship. In other words, in Mel-frequency cepstrum frequency bands are equispaced on the Mel scale, which is closer to human auditory characteristics compared to linear spaced cepstrum.

Lyrics

For a song, Lyrics are a very important component. Usually, it's easy to determine whether a song is expressing happiness or sadness from its lyrics. We can analyze the lyrics of a song with natural language processing methods to generate text features to describe the emotion in it [90, 51]. Several researches show that the accuracy of valence could be improved when using lyrics as one of the features [96, 52, 61, 106, 71].

In [44], researchers used language as the key feature, and studied the relationship between listeners' personal characteristics and their perceived emotion in pop and rock music. They proposed that if listeners understand the semantic content of the lyrics of a song, the agreement of their emotional annotation to this song increases and probably improves the models.

Extracting emotional features in text only is complicated because of the ambiguity of text content. Thus, lyrics are often used in combination with acoustic features or tags of the song.

2.3 Feature Extraction Tools

In order to extract audio features more easily and accurately, people developed some tools to assist MIR research. The tools that are commonly used are as follows:

MIRToolbox

MIRToolbox was developed by University of Jyväskylä. It is a set of integrated functions written in MATLAB that are used to extract music features from audio files [60]. It can extract a large number of audio features, both in low and high levels [80].

In [78], Panda et al. compared audio features extracted with different tools. The result shows that MIRToolbox features achieve arousal with R^2 attaining 60.3% and valence 25.7%. In the top 10 features for arousal, 7 were extracted with MIRToolbox

while 8 out of 10 were for valence. Later, they extracted audio features with different audio frameworks and used these feature sets, with annotations in datasets and supervised learning techniques to train and test different classifiers [79]. The results showed that when evaluating the performance of different tools separately, features extracted with MIRToolbox achieved higher accuracy. When combining the three feature sets together, the top 12 features that achieved the best accuracy, 9 were MIRToolbox features.

openSMILE

openSMILE is a feature extraction toolkit implemented in C++ by Technical University of Munich [37]. It integrates features from speech processing and Music Information Retrieval, which could help researchers in each field access and benefit from other fields.

The primary objective of openSMILE is real-time operation. So, it provides runtime benchmarks for various feature sets. It also supports real-time audio recording, subsequent incremental feature extraction, and real-time automatic analysis of speech and music signals.

Although openSMILE is mainly used for audio feature extraction, it can also be applied to some related signal processing and analysis. For example, physiological features like heart rate, EMG, or EEG signals, the speaker's personal information such as age, gender, personality, etc., and even the speaker's health condition, like pathological disorders or even psychiatric disorders like depression. OpenSMILE also contains music classification technology, which can be used in recognizing chorus segments, keys, rhythms, etc., identifying the genres of music and detecting music emotion

After extracting Low-Level Descriptors (LLD), openSMILE can apply a variety of filters, functionals and transformations to them. Every data vector can be processed by basic operations such as addition, multiplication and exponentiation, which enables users to create custom features by these operations. In this way, openSMILE became the benchmark of various research competitions [99]. MediaEval, one of

the competitions, used openSMILE as benchmark, which is where the data of the DEAM dataset comes from.

LibROSA

LibROSA is a Python package that is used for audio and music signal processing. It can be employed to realize basically the most common functions throughout the entire MIR field [68]. So, it is widely used for speech and music feature extraction in MIR research.

In [83], Raguraman et al. developed a LibROSA-based tool that can help people evaluate their performance when playing musical instruments. The tool detects notes, which is implemented with the function of feature extraction of LibROSA, and compares the features with the predefined features for notes with machine learning algorithms. This research field will lead to immense developments in computer-based music education technology. In [72], Mor et al. set up a method that can produce a high-fidelity translation across different musical instruments, genres and styles. The method first extracts pitch information with LibROSA and then compares the input pitch and the output pitch. The experiments show that the system performs better than human musicians in translation, and natural results with a completely seamless shift in semantic blending.

PsySound

PsySound is a software that provides a platform for analyzing not only acoustical features (e.g., loudness and pitch) but also psycho-acoustic information. At first, PsySound was developed by Cabrera for analyzing sound recordings for some psycho-acoustical models. Then he combined separate programs into a single and provided a simple interface [22], which made the second version of PsySound. The third version, which is the latest version at present, was published in 2007. It uses a logically sequenced user interface which makes it friendly for those inexperienced in programming. The output detailed numeric data enables users to use the results for other purposes like statistical analysis [24, 23].

In [94], researchers used PsySound to analyze the changes in psycho-acoustical features in some excerpts, and correlated these changes with mean changes in emotion recorded by LabVIEW. Cross-correlation analysis indicated the prediction of musical features on emotion varies greatly. That is, some features predict the emotion precisely in some excerpts but not significant in others. In [53], Hu et al. evaluated an emotion regression model based on fifteen acoustic features of five emotion-related musical aspects. Their experiments showed that loudness and timbre features extracted by PsySound performed effectively for both valence and arousal. The loudness feature achieves the best performance in terms of cross-dataset and overall regression. This indicates that using PsySound to model the human auditory system is for predicting arousal. Furthermore, dissonance features generated by PsySound showed a good performance in cross-dataset prediction.

Essentia

Essentia is a cross-platform, open-source library for audio analysis and audio-based MIR research. It is written in C++ and wrapped in Python for users who are familiar with Matlab or Python. Features extracted by Essentia could be divided into three groups: low-level features, rhythm features, and tonal features. It also includes the function to calculate statistical features like mean value, the median, root mean square, energy, etc. Essentia contains a number of executable extractors, which are used to calculate the music descriptors of audio tracks: time domain, spectrum, rhythm and tone descriptors. The results are returned in yaml and JSON formats [20, 19].

Essentia has been widely used in MIR research such as music classification, instrument detection, emotion classification, music recommendation and semantic auto-tagging [20]. In [10], Aljanaki et al. extracted features with Essentia and openSMILE to predict the emotion of music segments separately with Gaussian Process regression. The evaluating results indicated that features from Essentia performed much better than openSMILE in terms of arousal. In [45] and [46], researchers compared the performance between features extracted by Marsyas and Essentia. The

results indicated that the two frameworks were comparable in predicting arousal, but using tonal and rhythm features of Essentia (which are not available in Marsyas) greatly improved the prediction of valence.

In recent years, Essentia-based systems have been increasingly used in the Music Information Retrieval Evaluation eXchange (MIREX) campaigns. Usually, they perform among the best ones [20].

2.4 Music-Emotion Datasets

In recent years, the research of MER has received more and more attention. Datasets in this field have been constantly created. In this section, we introduce some widely known and with high quality. These datasets are annotated with perceived emotion in the dimensional approach.

AMG1608

AMG1608 is made of 1608 30-second music clips and annotations from 665 subjects [97]. The music in the dataset are contemporary Western music listed with their emotion tags defined by music editors. Then these tags were transferred into V-A value with tag2VA algorithm [97] as the initial value of each song. Next, select multiple songs from each quadrant of V-A space randomly, while ensuring that each song is evenly distributed in the four quadrants of V-A space. Finally, 1608 clips are remained.

Every subject would annotate several groups of segments. Each group contains 12 segments, one of which will appear twice to evaluate the annotation quality. If the annotated V-A values of the two identical songs differ too much, the annotation of this group will be excluded.

The dataset is relatively large enough, whether in terms of the quantity of songs, the number of participants recruited, or the volume of annotations provided by each participant. In the annotation collecting process, a quality evaluation mechanism is set to ensure the quality of annotation.

CH818

CH818 dataset is a Chinese dataset [54]. It contains 818 30-second clips of Chinese pop-song released from 1987 to 2010. The music were collected from albums on top lists, which means the songs were popular and influential. In order to make the songs in the dataset diversified, one song was randomly selected from each of the 818 collected albums. In each song, the extracted segment is the strongest emotional part that is automatically detected by the sum of the square of predicted values of valence and arousal.

The clips were annotated by three students in a music school, Master’s or senior undergraduates. They were born and raised in Mainland China, meaning they had a solid Chinese cultural background. Each of them took a training session before annotating. Then, they annotated all 818 songs independently. Besides the dimensional V-A model, they tag the clips with categorical labels.

The CH818 dataset is very unbalanced. But with the annotation in both dimensional and categorical approaches, the dataset could facilitate the study of the relationship between dimensional and categorical annotations.

CCMED-WCMED

CCMED-WCMED [38] consists of two parts: Chinese classical music excerpts (CCMED) and Western classical music excerpts (WCMED). CCMED contains 400 excerpts gathered from Chinese classical music recordings, and WCMED contains 400 excerpts collected from Western classical music recordings. The instrumentation of each subset is diverse to perform various timbres. The length of each excerpt varies from 8-20 seconds.

There were A total of 989 subjects from 21 countries participated in annotating. The annotation was not made by rating an absolute value in arousal and valence in a V-A plane for each song. Subjects were asked to pairwise comparisons and decide which excerpt has higher arousal/valence. The ranking work was completed by the researchers.

CCMED-WCMED evenly contains Chinese classical music and Western classical music, which could promote further study of these music from different traditions. In addition, annotating by pairwise comparison simplifies the annotation process and improves the reliability among annotators.

EMOPIA

EMOPIA [55] is a dataset that focuses on perceived emotion in pop piano music. It contains 1,087 music clips from 387 piano solo performances of pop music. The dataset provides both audio (through YouTube links) and MIDI modalities.

The annotation was made by four annotators. Compared to labeling values precisely in four quadrants of V-A space to indicate a further comparison of arousal and valence, EMOPIA simply classifies the perceived emotion into four classes corresponding to the four quadrants in Russell's V-A space.

2.5 Machine-Learning Algorithms

Machine learning is the science of training machines to analyze and learn from data in the way we humans do [5]. Based on the idea that systems can learn from data, recognize patterns, and make decisions, we develop machine-learning algorithms to research and dig deep features and information in data, and then use the information to create models to help us making predictions of the data [3, 5]. In this section, we will introduce some Machine-Learning algorithms that are used in analyzing the data in the DEAM dataset. As these machine-learning algorithms are tools but not objects for the study in this article, we only introduce the principles of these algorithms, but do not discuss the math details behind them.

2.5.1 Manifold Learning

Manifold learning is a nonlinear dimensional reduction method. Due to the limitations of the internal characteristics of the data, some high-dimensional data will produce dimensional redundancy, so the data can be uniquely represented in lower-

Figure 4: Circle in 2-dimensional coordinates and polar coordinate

dimensional space.

For example, there is a circle of radius r in a 2-dimensional plane with its center at the point $(0,0)$ (Fig 4 left). Actually, the circle consists of a series of points with a distance of r from the origin (black points). Except for these points, all other points on the 2-dimensional plane are not on this circle (red points). That is to say, it is redundant to represent this circle with 2-dimensional coordinates. But if we use polar coordinate (Fig 4 right), this circle can be presented with only one parameter: radius. In this way, the representation of this circle is reduced from 2-dimensional to 1-dimensional. So, in fact, the circle in 2-dimensional space is a 1-dimensional manifold.

Figure 5: Calculate the distance between points A and B

In Fig 5, If we want to calculate the distance between two points $A(x_1, y_1)$ and $B(x_2, y_2)$, the distance should be calculated by

$$d = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2} \quad (2.1)$$

But if we want to know the distance between points A and B along the circle, it should be the arc length between these two points on the circle (the red curve).

Similarly, if there is a surface (flat or curved) in a 3-dimensional space, it will cause redundancy if we represent this surface with the three coordinate axes x, y, and z because many points in the 3-dimensional space are not on the surface. A typical example is “the Swiss Roll” (Fig 6)

Figure 6: The Swiss roll by Cayton [25]

The data we observed is 3-dimensional, which essentially is a 2-dimensional manifold. When calculating the distance between points A and B, they will be very close points if calculated by the Euclidean distance in the Euclidean space. But in fact, this calculation method can not reflect the nature of the data. From the figure, we can easily see that the distance should be the length between the points on the surface.

So, manifold learning is to reduce data dimensions from high-dimensional space to low-dimensional space, but with no information of data lost. In this dimension-reducing process, not only the distance but also the topology of the generated data are considered.

In practical application, each data point may contain hundreds or thousands of features, yet it can be expressed as a function of only a few fundamental parameters. This means the data points are essentially samples from low-dimensional manifolds embedded in high-dimensional spaces. We utilize manifold learning to reduce the dimension of the features, enabling a more concise representation of the data [25].

PCA

PCA is the abbreviation of *Principal Component Analysis*. The goal of PCA is to map high-dimensional data into a lower-dimensional space through a linear projection, and maximize the variance of data on the projected dimension. Because the value of variance represents the distribution of data. The greater the variance, the more significant the distribution characteristics of the data.

The *principal component* refers to the directions along which the variation changes the greatest [85], which makes these directions “principal” for the data. With these new components, the samples could be represented with relatively few variables compared to the original representation. Here we refer to Markus Ringnér’s example of a gene expression dataset to elaborate.

Fig 7(a) represents the cancer expression levels for two genes, of which the X axis and Y axis represent two genes that are related to breast cancer GATA3 and XBP1 respectively. The black dots represent negative while red is positive. Through PCA, we find the direction along which the data spread the fastest, which is the PC1 in Fig 7(b). The first principal component (PC1) is the direction in which the samples show the greatest variation. The second principal component (PC2) is the direction that is uncorrelated with PC1. We can see that PC1 and PC2 are linear combinations of original variables.

Now, the dimension can be reduced to a single dimension by projecting every sample onto PC1 as Fig 7(c) shows. This 1-dimensional representation has a good performance in classification.

The dataset totally contains the cancer expression levels for 8,534 genes for 105

Figure 7: An example of PCA by Ringnér [85]

samples in total. After applying PCA on all genes for all samples, Ringnér calculated the proportion of the variance in all genes in each principal component. Specifically, project all samples to each principal component, and calculate the variance of the value on it. Then we can get the ratio of variance on each component to the variance of all samples.

The results are shown in Fig 7(d). We can see that with only 104 components can we represent all the information of the original 8,534 variables. Normally, it is not necessary to reproduce a hundred percent of the original information, thus the number of variables can be further reduced.

So, with PCA, the original data could be presented with fewer dimensions and retain more information of the original data.

MDS

Multi-Dimensional Scaling (MDS) is a dimensional reduction method that maps data in a higher-dimensional to a lower-dimensional space while keeping the original

relative distance between every pair of points unchanged as much as possible [87]. The distance between samples in the original space is maintained in the low dimensional space, which keeps the relative spatial relationship of samples unchanged.

From the perspective of science and mathematics, distance represents the quantitative degree of distance between two objects. In other words, distance is a way to measure how related or closed between data samples [26, 48]. The smaller the distance, the more similar the two samples are. So, while reducing dimensions, MDS preserves the same high-dimensional data clusters and patterns in the low-dimensional space. Normally, the default distance is Euclidean distance, but it can be other distances like Manhattan distance, etc [73].

Fig 8 is an example of applying MDS on some points in a 3-dimensional space. It returns the embedded points in a 2-dimensional space. We can see that the relative distances of the points in the right plot basically kept unchanged.

Figure 8: Example of MDS by Mehreen Saeed [87]

MDS is not only an effective dimensional reduction technology, but also a data visualization technology [87]. When applying PCA, we already know everything about the data or feature in the high-dimensional space. But in some circumstances, like in psychological emotional applications, we can't depict mental activity or emotion with exact data. We only know the similarities, or dissimilarities, between different thoughts or emotions. In these cases, MDS provides a visual representation to show

how “similar” or “dissimilar” objects are in a set of samples.

In conclusion, MDS not only helps reducing dimensions effectively, but also very useful for data visualization and to identify important factors and dimensions that are hidden in the data.

t-SNE

The full name of t-SNE is *t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding*.[\[95\]](#) It is a dimensional reduction method that tries to maintain the probability distribution of data samples from higher dimensions in lower dimensions[\[8\]](#) Specifically, in t-SNE, we transform the “distance between samples” into a probability distribution. Each probability distribution corresponds to a “distance between samples” relationship. We aim to keep the probability distributions similar before and after dimensional reduction.

T-distribution is a continuous probability distribution similar to Normal distribution. Fig [9](#) is the chart of Normal distribution and t-distribution. We can see that t-distribution is slightly flatter than the Normal distribution. The flatness is decided by a parameter n . When n is large enough, the t-distribution is approximate to the Normal distribution.

Figure 9: Normal distribution curve (red) and t-distribution curve

T-SNE is mainly divided into three steps: high-dimensional calculation, low-dimensional

Figure 10: t-SNE High-dimensional calculation

calculation, and movement. [92, 108] We take Fig 10 as a simple example of the processing of t-SNE dimensional reduction.

Fig 10(a) is a set of data in a 2-dimensional plane. In the high dimension, we need to calculate the similarity between every pair of points. Take the point S_1 as an example, we use the t-distribution to calculate the distance between it and S_2 (Fig 10(b)). In this way, the points close to it have higher values in t-distribution, while the points farther have lower values. Fig 10(c) shows the calculation results of S_1 and all other points. Next, we need to normalize the similarity. Why normalization? Let's take a look at Fig 11. The orange cluster is more concentrated, so its t-distribution will be narrower than the purple. If we use the same standard to measure these two clusters, the adjacent points of the purple cluster will not be grouped together. After normalization, we will get a similarity matrix, (Fig 10(d)) where red represents high similarity and white represents low similarity.

Figure 11: Normalization

Next is to proceed with the low-dimensional calculation. First, we project all the points randomly on a straight line (1-dimension) (Fig 12(a)), and then use the t-distribution to measure the distance between every two points (Fig 12(b)). Finally, we calculate a similarity matrix for these randomly arranged points (Fig 12(c)).

Our goal is to make the low-dimensional similarity matrices resemble the high-dimensional similarity matrices as closely as possible. So we need to adjust the position of the points until low-dimensional similarity matrices are as similar to the high-dimensional similarity matrices as possible.

Figure 12: t-SNE Low-dimensional calculation

Compared to other dimensional reduction methods, t-SNE focuses more on preserving the local features of the original data. Moreover, because the points are *randomly* projected on the low dimension, each result of the dimensional reduction is different. Thus, t-SNE can hardly preserve the global structure and features of the data.

UMAP

UMAP stands for *Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection*. [69] Its core working principle is similar to t-SNE, to use graph-based algorithms to arrange data in lower dimensional spaces. First, it builds a high-dimensional graph to present the

relationship between data in high-dimensional space. Then, find projections that maintain these relationships in low-dimensional space. Meanwhile, to preserve their structures as similar as possible to those in high-dimensional space. [12, 102]

Fig 13 shows how UMAP builds a high-dimensional graph. Fig 13(a) is a set of data in a 2d-dimensional plane. UMAP extends a radius around each point like in Fig 13(b). If the radii of two points overlap, we establish a connection between them (Fig 13(c)). For every single point, the points that are connected to it are its neighbors. However, If a point is far away from all other points, there would be no point connected to it (the point in the middle in Fig 13(c)). If some points are very close in a specific region, a point may have too many neighbors in the given radius, which will make these points too connected (the points in the right in Fig 13(c)).

Figure 13: Explanation of high-dimensional graph building

To avoid these problems, UMAP uses a variable radius instead of a fixed radius. Variable radius has been proved by math that it will not cause any trouble. So, we set a larger radius in low-density regions and smaller in high-density regions like Fig 13(d). We assign a weight to the connection between each point and its neighbors

to indicate the connection probability of these two points. The points with longer distances have a smaller weight and a lower connection probability.

Next, we create a projection of the high-dimensional graph in a lower-dimension space. When creating the projection, we want to keep the weights on the connection between each point unchanged. We can imagine the edge between points as a spring, the bigger the weight, the stronger the spring. Points connected by high-weighted edges are more likely to remain connected in low-dimensional space, because the springs between them are more powerful to connect them together. Fig 14 is an example of UMAP that reduces data from 3-dimension to 2-dimension. Fig 14(a) is the original data. Fig 14(b) is the high-dimensional graph UMAP build. And Fig 14(c) is the result of UMAP dimensional reduction.

Figure 14: Example of UMAP

when applying manifold learning, we always face a paradox, that to make a trade-off between preserving the global structure and preserving the local structure of the data. So, in practical application, we often use PCA and MDS for data calculation and analysis, and use t-SNE and UMAP for data visualization.

2.5.2 Clustering

Clustering is a process to divide a set of objects into several subsets that are usually not intended to intersect, and the objects in the same group are relatively similar to each other than to those in other groups. Each group is called a cluster.

Clustering originated from Taxonomy, but it is not equal to classification. [7] Clustering is an unsupervised learning task. We don't know the label of the sample (data), and the number of categories is uncertain. The purpose of clustering is to aggregate the entire sample set into several groups according to the similarity between them. Samples with similarities are clustered into a group. Classification is a supervised learning task. The label of every sample is already known and the number of categories is fixed. We use these samples and their labels to train a learner and predict the category of unknown samples. [17]

Clustering can be used not only as a separate process to discover the internal distribution structure of data, but also as a precursor to other learning tasks such as classification. It is a common technique for statistical data analysis that is used in many fields like machine learning, pattern recognition, information retrieval, bio-informatics, etc [1].

Clustering is a subjective task. There are lots of ways to define "similarity" to group samples, which derives into different clustering algorithms. All these algorithms can be divided into two types. One is hard clustering, which means each data is clustered into one group for sure (100%) or not into a group at all (0%). The other is soft clustering. It is not absolutely certain whether a point belongs to a certain cluster, but the probability of this point belongs to the cluster. [30]

K-means

The K-means clustering algorithm was proposed by J.B. MacQueen in 1967. [64] Now, it is the most classic and widely used partition-based clustering algorithm. [6] K-means clustering is a distance-based clustering algorithm. It uses distance as an indicator of similarity between objects, which believes that the closer the distance between two objects, the greater their similarity.

K-means clustering considers that a class family is composed of objects that are close in distance, takes the center point as the center of mass, and categorizes the objects that are close to the center of mass into one class. The ultimate goal of K-means clustering is to obtain compact and independent clusters.

Figure 15: Flowchart of k-means clustering algorithm

The K-means clustering algorithm is an iterative process and a self-learning algorithm. The flow chart is shown in Fig 15.

Fig 16 is an example of the process of K-means clustering. First, we should determine the value of K, which represents the number of clusters we want, and then select K points randomly as initial cluster centers. Next, calculate the distance between every sample data and the K cluster centers, and divide the sample into the cluster represented by the center that is closest to it. After the classification of every sample is finished, we now have k clusters. For each cluster, we take the average value of all the samples in it as the new center of this cluster. At this time, all the sample points are divided into K clusters with the new centers. We again calculate the distance between points and centers to update clusters and the centers. The iteration will not end until the center no longer changes or the error is less than a certain range. Sometimes, we set the times of iterations. The clustering process ends when the set times of iteration are complete. [2]

Through the k-means clustering process above, we can see that there are two essential elements: K value and initial centers. To determine the K value, we can try different K to compare their clustering effects and select the best one, or combine them with of practical needs to determine the K value. For example, if we want to

divide some balls into basketball, football, and volleyball, then the K value should be 3.

Figure 16: K-means clustering process

DBSCAN

DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) was invented by Martin Ester et al. in 1996. [34] Unlike k-means or Agglomerative clustering, DBSCAN is a density-based clustering algorithm. Specifically, it determines the similarity of data objects by density instead of distance. DBSCAN defines a cluster as a dense area composed of points. It divides areas with sufficiently high density into clusters and discovers clusters of any shape in noisy spatial databases.

There are two essential parameters for DBSCAN, neighborhood radius r and minimum number of points $MinPoints$. [111, 31] We can use these two parameters to describe what is “dense” - when the number of points within the neighborhood radius r is greater than the minimum number of $MinPoints$, it is dense. The key idea is that for each point in a cluster, the neighborhood of a given radius must contain at least a minimum number of points.

With r and $MinPoints$, all data points can be divided into three categories. [74, 111]

1. Core point A point that has at least $MinPoints$ points within the neighborhood radius r . **2. Border point** A point that is not a core point, but has at least one Core point within its neighborhood radius r . **3. Noise point** A point that is neither a Core point nor a Border point. Fig 17 shows how to determine the Core point, Border point, and Noise point, which is an essential element of the DBSCAN algorithm.

Figure 17: Core point, Border point and Noise point [101]

With these basic ideas, we can apply the DBSCAN algorithm to data points. [101] First, we need to collect all core points in the data. Second, we deal with the core points. For every core point, if there is any point in its neighbor with radius r that has been clustered into one group, this core point should be clustered into the same group. If all points in its neighbor with radius r are not in any cluster, we set a new cluster with this core point. Next, we treat the rest non-core points. If there is one

or more core points in the neighbor with radius r of a non-core point, we cluster it into the core point's group. If there is no core point in its neighbor with radius r , it's a noise point.

To be noticed, for DBSCAN $MinPoints$ must be greater than or equal to 3. If $MinPoints=1$, every point is a core point, that is, every sample is a cluster class. It's meaningless for clustering. If $MinPoints=2$, any points in neighbor with radius r are merged, the result is the same as Agglomerative Clustering. Fig 18 is an example of applying the DBSCAN algorithm on a set of data points. We set $r=3$ and $MinPoints=4$.

Figure 18: Result of DBSCAN algorithm in uneven density data points

DBSCAN performs well when the density of the cluster is constant. But when the density of the data samples is uneven, there might be some errors like in Fig 19. The data was supposed to be clustered in 4 groups, but the data in the upper right are determined to be noise points because their density is lower than data in other clusters. So, OPTICS was developed to solve this problem.

Figure 19: Result of DBSCAN algorithm in uneven density data points

OPTICS

OPTICS stands for *Ordering Points To Identify Cluster Structure*. [13]. As mentioned in the last section, DBSCAN has difficulty identifying clusters in data of different densities. However, OPTICS solves this problem perfectly. So, we can consider OPTICS as an upgraded version of DBSCAN.

Besides the 2 parameters r and $MinPoints$, OPTICS defines two new distance concepts: *Core distance* and *Reachable distance*. [107] **Core distance** is the minimum distance that makes a given point a core point. If the given point is not a core point, It doesn't have a Core distance. **Reachability distance** is the distance between a Core point and another point. If the distance between them is smaller than the Core distance of this Core point, the Reachability distance should be the Core distance of this Core point. (Fig 20, $MinPoints=4$)

Figure 20: Core distance and Reachability distance

The OPTICS algorithm is shown in Fig 21: First, create two queues, a Neighbor

Figure 21: Flow chart of OPTICS algorithm

queue N and an Update queue U . N is to store the current processing point and its neighbors within radius r , arranged in ascending order according to the reachability distance. U is to store pending points and their "updated distance". Second, select an unprocessed point as the center point. If it is a core point, calculate the reachability distances of all unprocessed points in its neighbor. Arrange the points in ascending order according to the reachability distance and place them in N . If it is not a core point, its U is empty and moves to a new unprocessed point. Next, compare the reachability distance of every point in N to its "updated distance" in the previous step. Choose the smaller value as the new "updated distance" for the point. If a point in U in the previous step is not in N in the current step, keep the point and its "updated distance" unchanged and put it in U in the current step to continue waiting. Similarly, arrange the points in U in ascending order of their "updated distance". Take the point with the smallest "updated distance" as the center point of the next step. The smallest "updated distance" of this point is the distance between it and the current center point, which is the "final distance" in the OPTICS algorithm. For the first point and any point whose U of its previous step

is empty, we set their "final distance" as infinity. Continuously iterate the second and third steps until all data points are processed. [13, 107, 110, 109].

Obviously, it's much more complex than DBSCAN. We take the data in Fig 22 as an example. [58, 93, 107] The parameters are $r=3$ and $MinPoints=4$.

(a) Data points and parameters [58]

(b) Set up the Neighbor queue N and the Updated queue U

(c) 1st step, centered the point G

Figure 22: Example of OPTICS algorithm calculation (Part 1)

Parameters: $r = 3$ $MinPoints=4$

		queue N	queue U
Step	Center point	Unprocessed neighbors & Reachability distance	Waiting points & Updated distance
1	G	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
2	F	(H-2.2) (I-2.2) (J-2.2)	(H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)

Step 2, take F as the center point.
 The unprocessed points in F's neighbor {H, I, J}, have reachability distances in ascending order {(H-2.2), (I-2.2), (J-2.2)}. Reachability distances in queue N are all larger than in the queue U in the last step. So, the queue U remains unchanged in this step

(d) 2nd step, centered the point F

Parameters: $r = 3$ $MinPoints=4$

		queue N	queue U
Step	Center point	Unprocessed neighbors & Reachability distance	Waiting points & Updated distance
1	G	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
2	F	(H-2.2) (I-2.2) (J-2.2)	(H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
3	H	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)

Step 3. Take H as the center point.
 The unprocessed points in H's neighbor {I, J, K}, have reachability distances in ascending order {(I-1), (J-1), (K-3)}. Reachability distances of I and J in queue N are smaller than the queue U in the last step. So, we update the queue U to {(I-1), (J-1)}.
 A new point K is add. Since there is no K in previous steps, its value in queue U keeps the same as in queue N.

(e) 3rd step, centered the point H

Parameters: $r = 3$ $MinPoints=4$

		queue N	queue U
Step	Center point	Unprocessed neighbors & Reachability distance	Waiting points & Updated distance
1	G	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
2	F	(H-2.2) (I-2.2) (J-2.2)	(H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
3	H	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)
4	I	(J-1.4)	(J-1) (K-3)

Step 4. Take I as the center point.
 The unprocessed points in I's neighbor is only {(J-1.4)}. Reachability distances of J is larger than in the queue U in the last step. So, the queue U is still {(J-1)}.
 K is not in I's neighbor, so we keep it in queue U unchanged.
 Because J in the queue U is smaller than K, it is the only choice for the next step as the center point.

(f) 4th step, centered the point I

Parameters: $r = 3$ $MinPoints=4$

		queue N	queue U
Step	Center point	Unprocessed neighbors & Reachability distance	Waiting points & Updated distance
1	G	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
2	F	(H-2.2) (I-2.2) (J-2.2)	(H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
3	H	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)
4	I	(J-1.4)	(J-1) (K-3)
5	J	(K-2)	(K-2)

Step 5. J is the center point.
 The unprocessed points in J's neighbor is only {(K-2)}. Reachability distances of K is smaller than in queue U in the last step. So, we update the queue U to {(K-2)}.
 K is the only point left. So it is the only choice for the next step as the center point.

(g) 5th step, centered the point J

Figure 22: Example of OPTICS algorithm calculation (Part 2)

		queue N	queue U
Step	Center point	Unprocessed neighbors & Reachability distance	Waiting points & Updated distance
1	G	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
2	F	(H-2.2) (I-2.2) (J-2.2)	(H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
3	H	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)
4	I	(J-1.4)	(J-1) (K-3)
5	J	(K-2)	(K-2)
6	K	Not a core point	--

Step 6. K is the center point.
 K is not a core point. So the the queue N in this step is empty.
 The queue U is empty correspondingly.

Parameters: $r = 3$ $MinPoints=4$

(h) 6th step, centered the point K

		queue N	queue U
Step	Center point	Unprocessed neighbors & Reachability distance	Waiting points & Updated distance
1	G	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
2	F	(H-2.2) (I-2.2) (J-2.2)	(H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
3	H	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)
4	I	(J-1.4)	(J-1) (K-3)
5	J	(K-2)	(K-2)
6	K	Not a core point	--
7	E	Not a core point	--

Step 7. Select a new point randomly
 we take E as a new center point
 E is a non-core point. So, the Neighbor queue N and the Update queue U are empty in this step.

Parameters: $r = 3$ $MinPoints=4$

(i) 7th step, centered the point E

		queue N	queue U
Step	Center point	Unprocessed neighbors & Reachability distance	Waiting points & Updated distance
1	G	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)	(F-1.4) (H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
2	F	(H-2.2) (I-2.2) (J-2.2)	(H-1.4) (I-1.4) (J-2)
3	H	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)	(I-1) (J-1) (K-3)
4	I	(J-1.4)	(J-1) (K-3)
5	J	(K-2)	(K-2)
6	K	Not a core point	--
7	E	Not a core point	--
8	L	Not a core point	--
9	M	(N-1.4) (O-1.4) (P-1.4) (R-2) (Q-2.2) (S-2.2) (T-3)	(N-1.4) (O-1.4) (P-1.4) (R-2) (Q-2.2) (S-2.2) (T-3)
10	N	(O-1.4) (Q-1.4) (R-1.4) (P-2) (S-2.2) (T-3.2)	(O-1.4) (Q-1.4) (R-1.4) (P-1.4) (S-2.2) (T-3)
11	O	(P-1) (Q-1.4) (R-1) (S-1.4) (T-2)	(P-1) (Q-1.4) (R-1) (S-1.4) (T-2)
12	P	(R-1.4) (S-1.4) (T-2.2) (Q-2.2)	(R-1) (S-1.4) (T-2) (Q-1.4)
13	R	(Q-1) (S-1) (T-1)	(Q-1) (S-1) (T-1)
14	Q	(S-2) (T-1.4)	(S-1) (T-1)
15	S	(T-1.4)	(T-1)
16	T	No unprocessed point	--
17	D	(A-1.4) (B-1.4) (C-1.4)	(A-1.4) (B-1.4) (C-1.4)
18	A	(B-1.4) (C-1.4)	(B-1.4) (C-1.4)
19	B	(C-1.4)	(C-1.4)
20	C	No unprocessed point	--

Up to now, we have encountered and dealt with all possible conditions.
 The calculation of the remaining points can be finished by referring to the previous steps.
 This is the queue N and queue U after the calculation of all points.

(j) The final Neighbor queue N and Updated queue U

Figure 22: Example of OPTICS algorithm calculation (Part 3)

With the final Updated queue U , we can have the Reachability plot (Fig 23: the column "Center point" is the output sequence, and the corresponding "updated distance" in U is the output distance of every point. Since we set the neighborhood radius $r=3$, we put a $r=3$ on the plot. The points whose bar is shorter than r are non-noise points. These points are separated by some points whose bar is longer than r into several groups. Each group represents a cluster. Moreover, we decided the Reachability distance of the point of every new group is infinite. So, those previous points of the first point of each cluster belong to this cluster, although their Reachability distance is larger than r (Fig 24).

Figure 23: Reachability plot

Figure 24: Clustering points with the Reachability plot

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

In this chapter, we will first introduce the dataset we studied. Then present the flow of our work and the algorithms we selected in each step.

3.1 DEAM Dataset

The MediaEval Database for Emotional Analysis of Music (DEAM) is one of the largest available datasets of dynamic annotations [11]. It contains 1802 music pieces, from various Western popular music genres. The dataset consists of 3 main parts: Music Database, Annotations, and Features.

3.1.1 Music Database

The music database in DEAM is from several music platforms: *freemusicarchive.org* (FMA), *jamendo.com*, and medleyDB dataset [18]. All the music in DEAM is royalty-free. There are 1744 clips of 45 seconds and 58 full-length songs. The songs are from *rock, pop, soul, blues, electronic, classical, hip-hop, international, experimental, folk, jazz, country, world, rap* and *reggae*.

In 2013, there were 744 clips in the dataset. Every clip lasts 45 seconds. In 2014, 1000 new 45-second clips were added to the database. All the clips are extracted from random starting points. In 2015, 58 complete songs were added but no longer

clips. The composition of music data in the DEAM dataset is shown in Table 1.

Year	2013	2014	2015
No. of songs/clips	744	1000	58
Length of every song/clip	45s	45s	varied
Total length	9h 18min	12h 30min	3h 46min

Table 1: Summary of songs/clips data from 2013 to 2015

To ensure the quality of both the music and the dataset, all music were manually checked first. Those with poor recording quality, containing speech or noise were removed. In order to make data balanced, a maximum of 5 songs per artist are retained in the database. For the 58 full-length songs, only those with emotional fluctuation remained in the dataset.

All the music, both clips and full-length songs, are in MPEG layer 3 (MP3) format. The sampling rate is 44100Hz. They are available online, and are also provided in the dataset package [91].

3.1.2 Data Annotation

The annotation includes dynamic annotation and the annotation for the entire song. The dynamic annotation refers as the song plays, the annotator dynamically annotates the arousal and valence at the current moment. After dynamic annotations were made, the annotators were asked to annotate the entire music on a nine-point scale on arousal and valence separately.

The annotations were collected with MTurk (<http://www.mturk.com>), via a web interface, ranging from -10 to 10. In order to obtain high-quality annotations in the dataset, all workers should take a test first. Only those who passed the test, which means they understand the annotation task thoroughly and have the ability to produce good quality annotation, could participate in the formal annotation works.

Because the annotation sampling rate varied with browser and computer functions, the researchers re-sampled the annotations to 2Hz, and normalized the annotations

meanwhile. Then, they generated the average and the standard deviation of the annotations to show the distribution and the margin of error of annotations.

After each batch was finished annotating, the researchers would make a double-check on the consistency between the annotators in this batch. Then, assigned an increasing qualification score to allow the workers to work on the next batch.

In 2013 and 2014, every segment was annotated by at least 10 people. In 2015, every song was annotated by 5 people, 3 of them were from the most successful annotators in previous years and the other 2 were lab workers.

3.1.3 Music Feature-set

The DEAM dataset provides a series of feature sets as a baseline. The features were extracted from non-overlapping windows of 500ms, with a frame size of 60ms and a step size of 10ms. For every 500ms segment, there are 260 features in total, consisting of the mean and standard deviation of 65 low-level acoustic descriptors extracted by openSMILE (<http://opensmile.sourceforge.net/>), and their first-order derivatives. [36, 89]

The 65 features include **MFCCs**, **Basic Acoustic Features** (Fundamental Frequency, voicing probability, Jitter, Shimmer, Energy, Zero-crossing Rate, Harmonics-to-Noise Ratio), **Spectral Features** (Centroid, Flux, roll-off, Entropy, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Slope, Sharpness), and **Band-pass Filtered Spectral Features**.

3.1.4 Data Evaluation

The dataset was evaluated for its annotations consistency, the performance of different machine learning algorithms on every year's data, the machine learning algorithms on the same feature sets, and different feature sets with the same machine learning algorithms.

Annotation Consistency

The annotation consistency was evaluated with two measurement methods, Cronbach’s alpha of each song annotation sequence, and the coefficient of determination for a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) of annotations across annotators.

Cronbach’s alpha is a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely a set of items are connected as a group. A GAM is a generalized linear model whose linear predictor involves the sum of smooth functions of the covariates, it allows the non-normal error distribution of the response variable.

The results of annotation consistency are shown in Table 2

Year	2013	2014	2015
Total length	9h 18min	12h 30min	3h 46min
Cronbach’s α for arousal	.28 \pm 0.28	.31 \pm 0.30	.66 \pm 0.26
GAM’s R^2 for arousal	.13 \pm 0.10	.14 \pm 0.11	.44 \pm 0.19
Cronbach’s α for valence	.28 \pm 0.29	.20 \pm 0.24	.51 \pm 0.35
GAM’s R^2 for valence	.13 \pm 0.10	.10 \pm 0.08	.37 \pm 0.21

Table 2: Annotation consistency of each year, taken from [11]

Performance of data in every year

The researchers compared the performance of the different methods with two evaluation metrics: Pearson’s correlation coefficient, which is used to measure whether the change direction is guessed correctly, and root mean square error (RMSE), which is used to measure the distance between the prediction and true emotion of a song. They calculated the distance between the ground truth and the predicted values for each song, and averaged across the songs.

Table 3 shows the algorithms that perform the best for arousal and valence in each year. In 2013, solutions based on LSTM-RNN performed the best, both in terms of arousal and valence. In 2014, solutions based on LSTM-RNN performed the best for valence and the second best for arousal. In 2015, solutions based on LSTM-RNN performed the best both for arousal and valence like in 2013.

Authors	Year	Algorithm	Performance
[98]	2013	Bi-directional long-short term memory with recurrent neural network	$\rho_A = 0.31, \rho_V = 0.19$
[66]	2013	Gaussian Processes	$\rho_A = 0.11, \rho_V = 0.06$
[9]	2013	Support vector regression	$\rho_A = 0.14, \rho_V = -0.01$
[65]	2014	Kalman filtering	$\rho_A = 0.21, \rho_V = 0.17$
[29]	2014	Long-short term memory	$\rho_A = 0.35, \rho_V = 0.20$
[104]	2014	Continuous conditional random field	$\rho_A = 0.23, \rho_V = 0.12$
[103]	2015	Bi-directional long-short term memory with recurrent neural network	$\rho_A = 0.66, \rho_V = 0.15$
[103]	2015	Multiscale bi-directional long-short term memory with recurrent neural network	$\rho_A = 0.63, \rho_V = 0.15$
[47]	2015	Linear regression and smoothing	$\rho_A = 0.65, \rho_V = 0.01$

Table 3: Historic performance metrics in the Mediaeval contest for regression (2013-2014). ρ stands for Pearson’s correlation coefficient for A (arousal) and V (valence), taken from [43, 11].

Evaluation of Machine-Learning Algorithms

To evaluate the performance of different machine-learning algorithms, researchers compared the results of different algorithms on the same feature set, which is the baseline features used in 2015.

Almost all the best solutions are either based on LSTM-RNN networks or SVR. These algorithms perform quite well on arousal, but not very good in valence. It’s basically because that valence is harder to model and evaluate than arousal. For all approaches, although their correlation coefficients are different, they show almost the same performance in RMSE for arousal, which indicates that these algorithms probably have reached some kind of upper limit with the combination of feature sets and annotations.

Evaluation of Feature-sets

The features used were some widely known features, such as tempo, loudness, MFCCs, and low-level spectral features that related to timbre, which are also com-

monly used features in emotion recognition fields.

Three new features were proposed in 2014 [57]: compressibility features that describe how much the audio can be compressed, median spectral band energy that describes the audio spectral bandwidth, and edge direction histograms on the mel-frequency spectrogram.

The machine-learning algorithm the researchers used was LSTM-RNN, which performed the best in previous years. The network consists of 3 hidden layers with 250, 150, and 50 nodes respectively. In each layer, three elements were used: the number of memory blocks, the learning rate, and the standard deviation of the Gaussian noise that applied to the input activations. Before adding the next layer, each layer was pre-trained in a supervised manner. Finally, trained the whole network again. The results were evaluated with 20-fold cross-validation.

Table 4 presents the evaluation of the feature sets for both valence and arousal. The best performance of valence is a baseline feature set with feature selection, which could increase the valence recognition to the best level [81].

The transformation on the baseline feature set projects high-dimensional feature vectors to a lower-dimensional space, which makes the feature vectors for similar songs closer to the low-dimensional space, both in terms of valence and arousal [11]. Therefore, this transformation method makes it perform the best in arousal.

	Method	RMSE	ρ	ρ_C
Arousal	HKPOLYU [62]	.22 ± .12	.39 ± .41	.24 ± .26
Valence	JUNLP [81]	.27 ± .13	.19 ± .35	.08 ± .15

Table 4: Feature-set perform the best Arousal and Valence [11]

3.2 Methodology

In this section, we will first present the workflow of annotation processing. And then, take the annotation of the song #2 in the dataset as an example to demonstrate the detail of each step.

3.2.1 Work Flow

Fig 25 presents the whole process of how we select annotation data in the dataset, with the methods we used listed in every step.

Figure 25: Workflow of annotation processing

3.2.2 Details in Every Step

In the DEAM dataset, arousal and valence are annotated separately. So, there are two sets of annotation data for every music piece, for arousal and valence respectively. However, the two annotations are processed independently, which means for the same music piece, the selected annotations for arousal and valence are probably from different annotators. To demonstrate it clearly, we will present the selecting process of arousal and valence annotation on the song #2 simultaneously.

Fig 26 is the original arousal and valence annotation on the song #2 from 10 annotators in the DEAM dataset. Each line represents a worker's annotation scoring at this time point.

Step 1: Quantization

Quantization is a process of dividing the amplitude of the input data into a finite number of non-overlapping sub-intervals, each represented by a specific quantized value, to obtain better benefits (decrease memory consumption, speed up calculations, etc.) at the cost of small precision loss. The difference between adjacent

Figure 26: Arousal and Valence annotation for song #2

quantized values is called the quantization step or step-size. When the input signal falls within a particular sub-interval, it is output as the corresponding quantized value. Thus, the input signal is transformed into an approximate signal with a limited number of discrete value levels.

In this step, we set the quantization step (q) to 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 150, and 200 as experimental data for the quantization parameters. Fig 27 is the quantization result of original Arousal and Valence annotations for the song #2, with a quantization step of 10.

Figure 27: Arousal and Valence annotations after quantization ($q=10$)

Step 2: Manifold Learning

After quantization, we use manifold learning algorithms to reduce the annotation into 2-dimension. In this step, we employ PCA, MDS, t-SNE, and UMAP. Besides these four algorithms, we take into consideration not using manifold learning in our experiment. That is, go to the next step directly after quantization.

Fig 28 is the result of manifold learning (*PCA*) on the quantization results. Each

point represents a worker, and the color corresponds to the lines in the original annotations. We can see that after manifold learning, the lines that change over time are converted into independent points.

Figure 28: Arousal and Valence annotations after manifold learning (*PCA*)

Step 3: Clustering

In Fig 28, we can see that some points are closer to each other, representing annotations that are more similar, while some are not. We need a scientific and unified method to gather closer points into clusters. A proper clustering algorithm can gather points that are more similar together, and meanwhile more sensitive to noisy points. In this step, we apply K-means, DBSCAN, and OPTICS to the annotation data.

Fig 29 is the result of clustering based on the result in Step 2 (*K-means*). The red and black points each represent a cluster, and the black crosses are the centers of every cluster.

Step 4: Select a cluster

Now the annotations are separated into several clusters. We need to select a cluster as our experiment data. In this step, we use three different standards to pick the cluster: cluster with the least variance, cluster that most closest to the centroid (average distance of points closest to the center), and cluster with most annotators.

Based on the clustering result in Fig 29, we choose the cluster with the least variance, which are the red points in the figures. Corresponding to the color of the points in

Figure 29: Arousal and Valence annotations after clustering (*K-means*)

Fig 28 and Fig 26, the annotations we select are shown in 30. The solid lines are the annotations we select from the original annotation data, and the light-dotted lines are those we don't want.

Figure 30: Arousal and Valence annotations selected

Step 5: Performance with selected annotations

Now, we have a new set of annotation data, which is a subset of the original annotation. We will compare the performance of the original and selected annotations. Specifically, using the same baseline method and evaluation metrics as the researchers used in calculating baselines, to test the performance with the mean value of the selected annotations.

The baseline method utilizes a multi-linear regression model, with openSMILE features in 3.1.3

Chapter 4

Results

In order to figure out how the annotation selection affects the performance of emotion-predicting, we arrange and combine all the methods in each step, 315 in total, and apply every combination to the annotation data. In this chapter, we first evaluate the prediction performance of selected annotations, and present groups that perform the best. Then, we take the combination method that performs the best as a benchmark, to explore the impact of different algorithms on prediction performance at each step by controlling variables.

4.1 Annotation Performance

In addition to root mean square error (RMSE) and concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) in [11], we add coefficient of determination (R^2) and Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson r) as evaluation metrics to compare the performance before and after annotation selection. First, we calculate the four evaluation metrics between the predicted values and the ground truth on each song, and average the evaluation metrics across songs. Then compare the performance of the annotations selected with different methods.

We sort all the results by RMSE in ascending order, and present the best 3 groups of each year in Arousal and Valence respectively. The baselines on the bottom rows are

the reported values from [11], trained by multi-linear regression with openSMILE features. The paper didn't provide the baseline trained by the annotations of three years together. So we used the same model and features, trained all the annotations together and obtained an overall baseline.

4.1.1 Performance of Annotation in 2013

Table 5 and 6 show the 3 methods that performed the best on arousal and valence in 2013. Wherein **-u** represents UMAP, **-o** represents OPTICS, **-v** represents select the cluster with the least variance, and the last number parameter is the quantization steps. We can see that **UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance** perform the best both on arousal and valence. With different q values, the values are slightly different.

Compared to the baseline, the selected annotations perform a little better in RMSE, both on arousal and valence. The central value of RMSE has slightly decreased, with a significant decrease in standard deviation. The value of CCC has significantly increased. Indicating that the annotation selection process makes an improvement in the prediction performance.

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-u -o -v -10	0.219 ± 0.022	0.427 ± 0.108	0.663 ± 0.068	0.637 ± 0.053
-u -o -v -200	0.220 ± 0.023	0.427 ± 0.120	0.665 ± 0.074	0.639 ± 0.057
-u -o -v -50	0.221 ± 0.021	0.431 ± 0.117	0.667 ± 0.073	0.641 ± 0.054
Baseline	0.25 ± 0.11	–	–	0.16 ± 0.36

Table 5: Best 3 performance on Arousal in 2013

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-u -o -v -150	0.217 ± 0.025	0.201 ± 0.179	0.483 ± 0.098	0.425 ± 0.066
-u -o -v -200	0.218 ± 0.025	0.196 ± 0.178	0.478 ± 0.099	0.418 ± 0.068
-u -o -v 20	0.219 ± 0.024	0.193 ± 0.172	0.475 ± 0.097	0.416 ± 0.067
Baseline	0.23 ± 0.10	–	–	0.06 ± 0.30

Table 6: Best 3 performance on Valence in 2013

4.1.2 Performance of Annotation in 2014

Table 7 and 8 show the 3 methods that perform the best on arousal and valence in the year 2014. Wherein **-t** represents t-SNE, **-u** represents UMAP, **-o** represents OPTICS, **-v** represents select the cluster with the least variance, and the last number parameter is the quantization steps. We can see that **UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance** also performs the best both on arousal and valence. The performance of **t-SNE + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance** is comparable to the **UMAP-** method, only with a slightly larger standard deviation of R^2 and Pearson r.

Compared to the baseline, the performance of the selected annotations on RMSE is not as good as it is. Whether on arousal or valence, the central values of RMSE increase a little, but the standard deviation decrease a lot. However, the CCC values show a significant increase compared to the baseline, and higher than in 2013, both on arousal and valence.

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-u -o -v -5	0.156 ± 0.015	0.567 ± 0.061	0.756 ± 0.039	0.736 ± 0.041
-t -o -v -5	0.156 ± 0.015	0.567 ± 0.065	0.756 ± 0.042	0.736 ± 0.045
-u -o -v -50	0.157 ± 0.015	0.579 ± 0.059	0.765 ± 0.036	0.748 ± 0.036
Baseline	0.14 ± 0.06	–	–	0.18 ± 0.36

Table 7: Best 3 performance on Arousal in 2014

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-u -o -v -100	0.182 ± 0.012	0.322 ± 0.091	0.576 ± 0.063	0.521 ± 0.050
-u -o -v -10	0.182 ± 0.012	0.316 ± 0.093	0.572 ± 0.064	0.518 ± 0.049
-u -o -v -150	0.182 ± 0.013	0.320 ± 0.090	0.575 ± 0.062	0.519 ± 0.051
Baseline	0.10 ± 0.06	–	–	0.11 ± 0.34

Table 8: Best 3 performance on Valence in 2014

4.1.3 Performance of Annotation in 2015

Table 9 and 10 are the 3 methods that performed the best on arousal and valence in 2015. Wherein **-m** represents MDS, **-p** represents PCA, **-o** represents OPTICS, **-n** represents to select the cluster with most annotators, and **-v** represents the cluster with least variance. We can see that **MDS + OPTICS + Cluster with most annotators** performs the best on arousal. The next two methods, **UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance** and **t-SNE + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance** perform exactly the same. Yet, on the whole, there are basically no differences in the four evaluation metrics of the three methods. On valence, the methods **UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with most annotators** and **t-SNE + OPTICS + Cluster with most annotators** perform basically the same in RMSE. However, the R^2 values appear negative, which is not an ideal result.

Compared to the baseline, the performance of the selected annotations decreases in RMSE, both on arousal and valence. The CCC values have increased, but not as good as in 2013 and 2014.

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-m -o -n -100	0.222 ± 0.039	0.319 ± 0.278	0.618 ± 0.133	0.567 ± 0.157
-u -o -v -50	0.225 ± 0.047	0.320 ± 0.205	0.615 ± 0.107	0.566 ± 0.131
-t -o -v -50	0.225 ± 0.047	0.320 ± 0.205	0.615 ± 0.107	0.566 ± 0.131
Baseline	0.14 ± 0.06	–	–	0.37 ± 0.26

Table 9: Best 3 performance on Arousal in 2015

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-u -o -n -20	0.281 ± 0.057	-0.063 ± 0.319	0.343 ± 0.204	0.287 ± 0.182
-t -o -n -200	0.281 ± 0.063	-0.073 ± 0.387	0.312 ± 0.238	0.260 ± 0.227
-t -o -n -10	0.281 ± 0.071	-0.115 ± 0.347	0.301 ± 0.221	0.249 ± 0.200
Baseline	0.18 ± 0.09	–	–	-0.01 ± 0.38

Table 10: Best 3 performance on Valence in 2015

4.1.4 Overall Performance of All Annotation

After evaluating the performance of each year’s annotation separately, we group all the annotations from the three years together, that is, all the annotation in the dataset, to evaluate their overall performance.

In table [11](#) and [12](#), we can see that the best methods, both on arousal and valence, are still **UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance** and **t-SNE + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance**. Of these best performances, the evaluation metrics tend to be stable.

Compared to the baseline, which represents the performance of all the annotations, the selected annotations perform almost the same as the baseline both in terms of RMSE and CCC. Overall, although there are slight differences, the annotation selection process does not produce significant improvement or decrease in the performance of all annotations.

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-u -o -v -100	0.207 ± 0.019	0.463 ± 0.114	0.686 ± 0.068	0.651 ± 0.056
-u -o -v -150	0.207 ± 0.019	0.461 ± 0.114	0.684 ± 0.068	0.649 ± 0.056
-t -o -v -100	0.207 ± 0.019	0.461 ± 0.116	0.684 ± 0.069	0.649 ± 0.057
Baseline	0.207 ± 0.020	0.462 ± 0.117	0.685 ± 0.069	0.650 ± 0.057

Table 11: Best 3 performance on Arousal in Overall

Parameters	RMSE	R^2	Pearson r	CCC
-u -o -v -10	0.222 ± 0.028	0.200 ± 0.059	0.462 ± 0.050	0.379 ± 0.047
-t -o -v -10	0.222 ± 0.028	0.199 ± 0.060	0.461 ± 0.050	0.379 ± 0.046
-u -o -v -150	0.222 ± 0.029	0.202 ± 0.060	0.464 ± 0.051	0.382 ± 0.049
Baseline	0.223 ± 0.029	0.201 ± 0.061	0.464 ± 0.052	0.382 ± 0.048

Table 12: Best 3 performance on Valence in Overall

4.2 Comparison of Parameters

Based on the results above, we found that the method **UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance** always performs outstandingly. So, in this section, we take this method as a basis to explore how different algorithms in each step impact the prediction performance by controlling variables. Additionally, in order to eliminate the potential bias introduced by focusing on the best-performing method, we also take one of the worst-performing methods, **UMAP + K-means + Cluster closest to centroid**, as a benchmark for the experiment.

4.2.1 Quantization Steps

Fig 31 and Fig 32 show the RMSE performance for predicting arousal and valence as the quantization steps increase, using the methods UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance and UMAP + K-means + Cluster closest to centroid, across the annotation data for 2013, 2014, and 2015 separately, as well as the combined annotations from all three years.

Overall, the RMSE curves in Fig 31 are more stable than in Fig 32, which further confirms that the method UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with the least variance performs better than the other. Additionally, we can observe that across all years, when the q value is small, the RMSE fluctuates slightly. As q increases, the RMSE performance tends to stabilize. Therefore, we will take the q value as 50 when analyzing the impact of other parameters in the following experiments.

In 2013, the RMSE values for arousal and valence were very close. In 2014, there was a slight difference. By the year 2015, the difference further increases, and the error margins become significantly larger. But when the annotations from all years are tested together, the difference between arousal and valence is reduced and the error margin also decreases.

Figure 31: RMSE of different q values, with fixed UMAP + OPTICS + Cluster with least variance.

Figure 32: RMSE of different q values, with fixed UMAP + K-means + Cluster closest to centroid.

4.2.2 Manifold Learning Algorithms

Fig 33 and Fig 34 show the RMSE performance for predicting arousal and valence with different manifold learning methods on the annotation data in different years separately and combined together, with methods in other steps keep the same, OPTICS + Cluster with least variance + $q=50$ and K-means + Cluster closest to centroid + $q=50$ respectively. As mentioned before, we also tried not applying manifold learning on the annotation data and proceeding to the next steps directly.

In Fig 33, we can see that no matter which method is used, the RMSE values of arousal and valence are both reduced in all years compared to not using manifold learning, and the performances of the four methods in each year are very similar. It indicates that applying manifold learning algorithms on annotations can improve the predicting performance of the model.

However, Fig 34 shows that compared with not applying manifold learning methods, PCA and MDS could enhance the model's performance, and their performance is roughly the same. However, when using t-SNE or UMAP, the RMSE values increase significantly. It means the model's performance decreases with these two algorithms. And we can further know that UMAP performs worse than t-SNE.

As we have seen before, the RMSE values for arousal and valence in 2013 are very close. Then in 2014, the values were slightly different. In 2015, the difference further widened and the error margins increased. When combining the annotations of all years together, the difference between arousal and valence and the error margins are all reduced.

4.2.3 Clustering Algorithms

Fig 35 and Fig 36 present the performance of the model in predicting arousal and valence in each year using clustering methods of K-means, DBSCAN, and OPTICS, with the parameters in other steps remaining unchanged. Fig 35 is under the condition of UMAP + Cluster with least variance + $q=50$ and Fig 36 is UMAP + Cluster closest to centroid + $q=50$.

Figure 33: RMSE of different manifold learning methods, with fixed OPTICS + Cluster with least variance + $q=50$.

Figure 34: RMSE of different manifold learning methods, with fixed K-means + Cluster closest to centroid + $q=50$.

The two figures indicate that with different clustering methods, the overall performance of the model is relatively stable. Upon more detailed analysis, the performance of DBSCAN in Fig 35 is slightly inferior to that of K-means and OPTICS, which are closer. In Fig 36, the performance of the three clustering methods is almost indistinguishable.

On the whole, the difference between RMSE values between arousal and valence remains the same as in the previous analysis. The RMSE values of arousal and valence were close in 2013, then discrepancies got large in the years 2014 and 2015, and the differences decreased when all the annotations were combined together. The error margins in 2015 remained significant when compared to those in other years. However, the differences in 2014 and 2015 are not as obvious as before. It even drops when using K-means in Fig 35.

Figure 35: RMSE of different clustering methods, with fixed UMAP + Cluster with least variance + $q=50$.

Figure 36: RMSE of different clustering methods, with fixed UMAP + Cluster closest to centroid + $q=50$.

4.2.4 Cluster Selection Strategies

Fig 37 and Fig 38 show the prediction performance of the model on arousal and valence every year and overall, with different cluster selection strategies, namely "Closest to centroid", "Most annotators", and "Least variance", after applying UMAP + OPTICS + $q=50$ and UMAP + K-means + $q=50$ on annotation data respectively.

The two figures consistently indicate that the "Least variance" strategy has the lowest RMSE mean value, both in arousal and valence, across all year's annotation data. It means that the performance of this strategy in prediction is the best among the three strategies. The "Closest to centroid" strategy has the highest RMSE mean values, indicating it is the least effective of the three. The strategy "Most annotators" stays in the middle, not closer to either of the other two strategies.

Figure 37: RMSE of different cluster selection strategy, with fixed UMAP + OP-TICS + $q=50$.

Figure 38: RMSE of different cluster selection strategy, with fixed UMAP + K-means + $q=50$.

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Annotation Performance

From Table 5 and 6, we can see that in 2013, the selected annotation improved the prediction performance both in RMSE and the consistency between the predicted and actual values. This indicates that the method we proposed has a significant effect on improving the accuracy of prediction. In addition, this result also suggests that the annotation data in 2013 in the original dataset has a large room for improvement. We believe this is likely because the sample size for 2013 alone was not large enough, resulting in insufficient accuracy of the prediction. According to the instruction in [11], in 2013, 1,000 music clips and their annotations were collected at the beginning, 700 of them were used as training sets and 300 as validation sets for the baseline calculating. However, the compiler later found that there were duplicates in these 1,000 music clips. After removing the duplicates, only 744 data sets remained, meaning approximately one-quarter of the data was duplicated. These duplicates also have a certain impact on the accuracy of predictions.

By 2014, the performance of selected annotation on RMSE was slightly inferior to the baseline. It should be noted that the baseline calculation in [11] used the 744 non-duplicate clips in 2013 as the training set and the newly collected 1,000 clips as the validation set. That is to say, the baseline in 2014 was calculated with the

data of two years. Therefore, we can conclude that the increase in data volume has significantly improved the accuracy of predictions. However, in our experiment, the results in 2014 were derived from only the 1,000 new collected data, and the predicting performance of arousal is already very close to the baseline. In addition, the performance of selected annotation on CCC has been greatly improved. This also indicates, to some extent, the effectiveness of our method.

From Table 7 and Table 9, we found that the arousal baseline of RMSE in 2015 was the same as that in 2014. We speculate that the prediction of arousal has reached its maximum potential when calculating the baseline in 2014 with the linear regression model. However, the valence baseline of RMSE has increased from 0.10 ± 0.06 to 0.18 ± 0.09 , which means that the predicting performance has dropped. We believe that there might still be some room for improvement in valence prediction performance. In 2015, to calculate the baseline, the compiler selected 431 music clips from 1744 collected before as the training set, and 58 newly collected full-length songs as the validation set. The music data in 2013 and 2014 were 45-second clips from songs, while in 2015, according to [11], the compilers "selected songs which had emotional variation in them". The full-length songs naturally contain richer emotional information. Since the model was trained on short clips, it may have performed well on the training data but exhibited instability with the more complex emotional dynamics of full-length songs. This likely impacted the model's generalization ability, resulting in a wider range of errors in RMSE. This is evident in the data from 2015, where the error ranges are significantly larger, as shown in Figures 31-37. Additionally, the increase in CCC values is smaller in 2015 compared to 2013 and 2014, which we believe is also due to the same reasons.

From Table 9 and Table 10, we can also see that the prediction performance of the selected annotation in 2015 is significantly worse than the baseline. We think this should be due to insufficient data. In 2015, the music data was 58 full-length songs with a total length of only 3 hours and 46 minutes. Each song has only 5 annotations. According to the process of our experiment, after clustering and cluster selecting, the remaining annotation is too insufficient, which results in a lack

of representativeness. Ultimately it leads to underfitting when making predictions and the prediction accuracy is reduced significantly.

[11] didn't provide the prediction performance of all data merged together. So, the baselines in Table 11 and 12 are obtained by our replicating the model. The experiment shows that the performance of selected annotations is the same as that of all annotations both in RMSE and CCC values. It indicates that our experiment is effective. That is to say, we can use annotations that are more similar in the dataset to present all annotations for music emotion prediction.

5.2 Quantization Steps

From Fig 31 and Fig 32, we can see that the model's prediction performance shows slight fluctuations when the quantization level q is below 20. When the q value reaches 50 or higher, the model's prediction performance tends to be stable. Although the performance for 2015 shows significant fluctuations when q is in a higher value, we believe it is probably because of poor performance of the combination of UMAP + K-means + Cluster. In addition, as mentioned above, both the music data and annotations for each song are not enough, which leads to the fluctuation of the RMSE value here.

We analyze the impact of the q value in conjunction with the annotation collection process in [11]. When collecting annotations, the range set for the annotators was -10 to 10, with the score intervals displayed in the Annotation interface set to 1. Therefore, the annotators would subconsciously take 1 as the smallest unit when scoring. In this way, there are a total of 21 rating levels, which is sufficient for most people to rate their emotion levels. Although we take a q value of 50 for our other experiments, theoretically, a quantization level of 20 is already sufficient to retain the information from the original annotation.

5.3 Manifold Learning Algorithms

Comparing Fig 33 and Fig 34, we find that regardless of how other parameters are changed, the prediction performance of PCA and MDS consistently outperforms that of not applying manifold learning. We think it is because by reducing the dimensionality of data, manifold learning removes the redundant dimensions and noise in the data, preserves the most representative features, and reveals the true geometric relationships within the data. It enhances the model's generalization ability and reduces the risk of overfitting, which leads to a more accurate learning process and ultimately improves the model's performance in predictions.

However, the performance of t-SNE and UMAP differs significantly under different conditions. When we use OPTICS + Cluster with least variance + $q=50$, t-SNE and UMAP perform slightly better than PCA and MDS. But when we use K-means + Cluster closest to centroid + $q=50$, their performance declines a lot, even worse than that without manifold learning. Based on the comparison of different clustering algorithms in section 4.2.3 and the comparison of different cluster selection strategies in section 4.2.4, we speculate that the cluster selection strategy is the key factor that affects the prediction performance of different manifold learning algorithms. Opting for an appropriate cluster selection strategy can help t-SNE and UMAP achieve optimal prediction performance.

Overall, PCA and MDS exhibit stable performance, making them reliable choices when the impact of other parameters on prediction performance is uncertain. The unstable performance of t-SNE and UMAP also confirms what we introduced in section 2.5.1, that they are rarely used for dimensional reduction, but mainly for data visualization.

5.4 Clustering Algorithms

From Fig 35 and Fig 36, we can observe that the performance differences among the three clustering methods used in our experiment—OPTICS, K-means, and DBSCAN—are relatively minor. Fig 35 illustrates that OPTICS consistently shows

a slight edge over K-means, and K-means marginally outperforms DBSCAN. We believe the slight advantage of OPTICS comes from its ability to identify clusters of different densities. Emotions are highly subjective. Sometimes, even when perceiving the same emotion, different people may feel it with different intensities. In our experiments, the level of intensity is reflected in the annotator's rating, which is then expressed as the density of the annotation. Thus, the density-based advantages of OPTICS come into play. However, because of 5 or 10 annotations of each song or clip, the advantages are not very obvious.

Overall, although there are differences in performance among the three clustering methods, they are not substantial enough to significantly impact the overall predictive accuracy of the experiment.

When comparing the performance across each corresponding year in the two figures, it is evident that with all other parameters kept the same, the strategy "Cluster with least variance" consistently delivers better results than the "Cluster closest to centroid". This observation aligns with the findings discussed in Section [4.2.4](#), reinforcing the conclusion that clusters with the least variance are more effective for improving prediction accuracy.

5.5 Cluster Selection Methods

In Fig [37](#) and Fig [38](#), we can clearly see that among the three cluster selection strategies utilized in our experiment, "Closest to centroid" performs far inferior to the other two strategies. On the other hand, between the remaining strategies, "Least variance" shows a subtle but consistent advantage over "Most annotations." This advantage is particularly evident within the condition UMAP + OPTICS + $q=50$ in the year 2014, where "Least variance" stands out more clearly.

However, when examining the condition UMAP + Kmeans + $q=50$, we observe a slight reversal for the year 2015, where "Least variance" lags behind "Most annotations" in arousal prediction. This minor decline is likely due to the insufficient data available for 2015, as we discussed in previous sections. Despite this, the overall

consistency of "Least variance" across different conditions suggests that it remains a reliable choice, even if specific data limitations might occasionally impact its performance.

5.6 Conclusions

Based on the analysis above, we can conclude that our method demonstrates effectiveness in predicting music emotions. We prove that annotations that share similar characteristics provide a more consistent and reliable input for the model, helping it to better capture the underlying emotional patterns in the music. When the available music data is not sufficient enough, leveraging annotations that are more closely aligned in terms of emotional content can significantly enhance the accuracy of music emotion prediction.

However, if there are not enough annotations for each song or music clip—as was the case in the data from 2015, where each song had only 5 annotations—our method might end up excluding too many annotations in the selection process. This would result in a situation where the data for the model to learn from is insufficient, which leads to a reduction in the predictive accuracy.

For the four dimensionality reduction methods we used in the experiment, PCA and MDS exhibit more stable performance and can effectively improve the prediction accuracy of the model. However, the performance of t-SNE and UMAP is highly dependent on the methods in other steps. Specifically, when using OPTICS + Cluster with least variance + $q=50$, t-SNE and UMAP perform slightly better than PCA and MDS. But when using K-means + Cluster closest to centroid + $q=50$, t-SNE and UMAP show significantly worse performance compared to PCA and MDS, and even worse than the original annotation data without dimensionality reduction.

Among the three clustering methods, there is not much difference in performance. Although there are slight variations in the model's prediction accuracy when using different clustering methods, we believe it is not a decisive factor.

For the three Cluster Selection Strategies, the performance of "Least variance" is

always the best, followed by "Most annotations", and "Closest to Centroid" performs the worst. We believe that this is the decisive factor that influences the model's prediction performance.

For our research object, the DEAM dataset, we believe it possesses significant advantages. It encompasses a diverse range of music samples, involving different styles and genres, and contains rich emotional information, which enhances its representativeness and generalizability. Moreover, the annotations are made by well-trained annotators, ensuring their accuracy and reliability. As a result, the DEAM dataset holds substantial reference value for future research.

However, we cannot ignore that our works still have some limitations. For the same song, the selected annotations of arousal and valence might not from the same group of annotators, just as shown in Fig 30. Whether this factor affects the prediction performance, or if there are ways to mitigate its impact, can be further discussed in future work. Moreover, we only employed the Linear Regression model in our work. It would be valuable to explore how will our method perform on other models.

In the study of music emotion recognition, we always face the fact that the high subjectivity of emotions. So, how to obtain annotations that have high quality and consistency is a challenge that requires continuous effort and innovation to address. Another difficulty in this field is the complexity of music interpretation. Identifying and understanding emotion-related features in music is another challenge that demands in-depth research and exploration.

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Bibliography

- [1] Cluster analysis. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cluster_analysis#Connectivity-based_clustering_\(hierarchical_clustering\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cluster_analysis#Connectivity-based_clustering_(hierarchical_clustering)). 19 October 2022.
- [2] K means clustering – introduction. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/k-means-clustering-introduction/>. 24 Mar, 2023.
- [3] Machine learning – what it is and why it matters. https://www.sas.com/en_us/insights/analytics/machine-learning.html.
- [4] Timbre. <https://psychology.fandom.com/wiki/Timbre>.
- [5] What is machine learning? <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/resources/cloud-computing-dictionary/what-is-machine-learning-platform/>.
- [6] 数据挖掘学习笔记之k-means算法. https://blog.csdn.net/qq_43659234/article/details/108901771. 2020-10-02.
- [7] 聚类. https://baike.baidu.com/item/%E8%81%9A%E7%B1%BB/593695?fr=ge_ala. 2022-11-30.
- [8] H. Agarwal. t-sne (t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding algorithm). <https://www.enjoyalgorithms.com/blog/tsne-algorithm-in-ml>.
- [9] A. Aljanaki, F. Wiering, and R. Veltkamp. MIRUtrecht Participation in MediaEval 2013: Emotion in Music Task. Technical report, Utrecht University, MediaEval 2013 Workshop, 2013.

- [10] A. Aljanaki, F. Wiering, and R. C. Veltkamp. Mediaeval 2015: A segmentation-based approach to continuous emotion tracking. In *MediaEval*, 2015.
- [11] A. Aljanaki, Y.-H. Yang, and M. Soleymani. Developing a benchmark for emotional analysis of music. *PloS one*, 12(3):e0173392, 2017.
- [12] A. P. Andy Coenen. Understanding umap. <https://pair-code.github.io/understanding-umap/>.
- [13] M. Ankerst, M. M. Breunig, H.-P. Kriegel, and J. Sander. Optics: Ordering points to identify the clustering structure. *ACM Sigmod record*, 28(2):49–60, 1999.
- [14] L.-L. Balkwill and W. F. Thompson. A cross-cultural investigation of the perception of emotion in music: Psychophysical and cultural cues. *Music perception*, 17(1):43–64, 1999.
- [15] E. Benetos, M. Kotti, and C. Kotropoulos. Large scale musical instrument identification. In *4th Sound and music computing conference*, pages 283–286, 2007.
- [16] E. Bigand, S. Vieillard, F. Madurell, J. Marozeau, and A. Dacquet. Multidimensional scaling of emotional responses to music: The effect of musical expertise and of the duration of the excerpts. *Cognition & Emotion*, 19(8):1113–1139, 2005.
- [17] A. Bisht. ML : Classification vs clustering. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/ml-classification-vs-clustering/>.
- [18] R. M. Bittner, J. Salamon, M. Tierney, M. Mauch, C. Cannam, and J. P. Bello. Medleydb: A multitrack dataset for annotation-intensive mir research. In *ISMIR*, volume 14, pages 155–160, 2014.
- [19] D. Bogdanov, N. Wack, E. Gómez, S. Gulati, P. Herrera, O. Mayor, G. Roma, J. Salamon, J. Zapata, and X. Serra. Essentia: an open-source library for

- sound and music analysis. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia*, pages 855–858, 2013.
- [20] D. Bogdanov, N. Wack, E. Gómez Gutiérrez, S. Gulati, H. Boyer, O. Mayor, G. Roma Trepas, J. Salamon, J. R. Zapata González, X. Serra, et al. Essentia: An audio analysis library for music information retrieval. In *Britto A, Gouyon F, Dixon S, editors. 14th Conference of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR); 2013 Nov 4-8; Curitiba, Brazil.[place unknown]: ISMIR; 2013. p. 493-8*. International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR), 2013.
- [21] D. Bogdanov, M. Won, P. Tovstogan, A. Porter, and X. Serra. The mtg-jamendo dataset for automatic music tagging. 2019.
- [22] D. Cabrera et al. Psysound: A computer program for psychoacoustical analysis. In *Proceedings of the Australian Acoustical Society Conference*, volume 24, pages 47–54. AASC Melbourne, Australia, 1999.
- [23] D. Cabrera, S. Ferguson, F. Rizwi, and E. Schubert. Psysound3: a program for the analysis of sound recordings. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 123(5):3247, 2008.
- [24] D. Cabrera, S. Ferguson, and E. Schubert. 'psysound3': Software for acoustical and psychoacoustical analysis of sound recordings. Georgia Institute of Technology, 2007.
- [25] L. Cayton. Algorithms for manifold learning. *Univ. of California at San Diego Tech. Rep*, 12(1-17):1, 2005.
- [26] S.-H. Cha. Comprehensive survey on distance/similarity measures between probability density functions. *City*, 1(2):1, 2007.
- [27] S. Chase. What is melody in music? a complete guide. <https://hellomusictheory.com/learn/melody/>. May 11, 2022.
- [28] S. Chase. What is rhythm in music? a complete guide. <https://hellomusictheory.com/learn/rhythm/>. Accessed June 25, 2022.

- [29] E. Coutinho, F. Weninger, B. Schuller, and K. R. Scherer. The Munich LSTM-RNN Approach to the MediaEval 2014 "Emotion in Music" Task. Technical report, Technische Universität München, MediaEval 2014 Workshop, 2014.
- [30] A. CR. Exploring clustering algorithms: Explanation and use cases. <https://neptune.ai/blog/clustering-algorithms>. 25th April, 2023.
- [31] D. Dey. Dbscan clustering in ml | density based clustering. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/dbscan-clustering-in-ml-density-based-clustering/>. 23 May, 2023.
- [32] X. Downie, C. Laurier, and M. Ehmann. The 2007 mirex audio mood classification task: Lessons learned. In *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Music Inf. Retrieval*, pages 462–467, 2008.
- [33] P. Ekman. An argument for basic emotions. *Cognition & emotion*, 6(3-4):169–200, 1992.
- [34] M. Ester, H.-P. Kriegel, J. Sander, X. Xu, et al. A density-based algorithm for discovering clusters in large spatial databases with noise. In *kdd*, volume 96, pages 226–231, 1996.
- [35] E. Estrella. An introduction to the elements of music. <https://www.liveabout.com/the-elements-of-music-2455913>. 11/04/19.
- [36] F. Eyben, F. Weninger, F. Gross, and B. Schuller. Recent developments in opensmile, the munich open-source multimedia feature extractor. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia*, pages 835–838, 2013.
- [37] F. Eyben, M. Wöllmer, and B. Schuller. Opensmile: the munich versatile and fast open-source audio feature extractor. In *Proceedings of the 18th ACM international conference on Multimedia*, pages 1459–1462, 2010.
- [38] J. Fan, Y.-H. Yang, K. Dong, and P. Pasquier. A comparative study of western and chinese classical music based on soundscape models. In *ICASSP 2020-2020*

- IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 521–525. IEEE, 2020.
- [39] P. R. Farnsworth. A study of the hevner adjective list. *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism*, 13(1):97–103, 1954.
- [40] T. Fritz, S. Jentschke, N. Gosselin, D. Sammler, I. Peretz, R. Turner, A. D. Friederici, and S. Koelsch. Universal recognition of three basic emotions in music. *Current biology*, 19(7):573–576, 2009.
- [41] A. Gabrielsson and E. Lindström. The influence of musical structure on emotional expression. 2001.
- [42] A. Ghias, J. Logan, D. Chamberlin, and B. C. Smith. Query by humming: Musical information retrieval in an audio database. In *Proceedings of the third ACM international conference on Multimedia*, pages 231–236, 1995.
- [43] J. S. Gómez Cañón. *Human-centered machine learning from music emotion recognition*. PhD thesis, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, 2022.
- [44] J. S. Gómez Cañón, E. Cano, H. Boyer, E. Gómez Gutiérrez, et al. Joyful for you and tender for us: The influence of individual characteristics and language on emotion labeling and classification. In *Cumming J, Ha Lee J, McFee B, Schedl M, Devaney J, McKay C, Zagerle E, de Reuse T, editors. Proceedings of the 21st International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference; 2020 Oct 11-16; Montréal, Canada.[Canada]: ISMIR; 2020*. International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR), 2020.
- [45] J. Grekow. Audio features dedicated to the detection and tracking of arousal and valence in musical compositions. *Journal of Information and Telecommunication*, 2(3):322–333, 2018.
- [46] J. Grekow. Music emotion recognition using recurrent neural networks and pretrained models. *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, 57(3):531–546, 2021.

- [47] R. Gupta and S. Narayanan. Predicting Affect in Music Using Regression Methods on Low Level Features. Technical report, University of Southern California, MediaEval 2015 Workshop, 2015.
- [48] M. Harmouch. 17 types of similarity and dissimilarity measures used in data science. <https://towardsdatascience.com/17-types-of-similarity-and-dissimilarity-measures-used-in-data-science-3eb914d2681>. Mar 13, 2021.
- [49] K. Hevner. Expression in music: a discussion of experimental studies and theories. *Psychological review*, 42(2):186, 1935.
- [50] K. Hevner. Experimental studies of the elements of expression in music. *The American Journal of Psychology*, 48(2):246–268, 1936.
- [51] T. Hofmann. Probabilistic latent semantic indexing. In *Proceedings of the 22nd annual international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval*, pages 50–57, 1999.
- [52] X. Hu, J. S. Downie, and A. F. Ehmman. Lyric text mining in music mood classification. *American music*, 183(5,049):2–209, 2009.
- [53] X. Hu and Y.-H. Yang. Cross-dataset and cross-cultural music mood prediction: A case on western and chinese pop songs. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 8(2):228–240, 2017.
- [54] X. Hu and Y.-H. Yang. The mood of chinese pop music: Representation and recognition. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68(8):1899–1910, 2017.
- [55] H.-T. Hung, J. Ching, S. Doh, N. Kim, J. Nam, and Y.-H. Yang. Emopia: A multi-modal pop piano dataset for emotion recognition and emotion-based music generation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.01374*, 2021.
- [56] Y. E. Kim, E. M. Schmidt, R. Migneco, B. G. Morton, P. Richardson, J. Scott, J. A. Speck, and D. Turnbull. Music emotion recognition: A state of the art review. In *Proc. ismir*, volume 86, pages 937–952, 2010.

- [57] N. Kumar, R. Gupta, T. Guha, C. Vaz, M. Van Segbroeck, J. Kim, and S. S. Narayanan. Affective feature design and predicting continuous affective dimensions from music. In *MediaEval*, 2014.
- [58] P. S. KunstlicheIntelligenz. Clud7 example for optics clustering. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xqWsAk1by6c&t=71s>. Jun 2, 2022.
- [59] P. Lamere. Social tagging and music information retrieval. *Journal of new music research*, 37(2):101–114, 2008.
- [60] O. Lartillot, P. Toiviainen, and T. Eerola. A matlab toolbox for music information retrieval. In *Data analysis, machine learning and applications*, pages 261–268. Springer, 2008.
- [61] C. Laurier, J. Grivolla, and P. Herrera. Multimodal music mood classification using audio and lyrics. In *2008 seventh international conference on machine learning and applications*, pages 688–693. IEEE, 2008.
- [62] Y. Liu, Y. Liu, and Z. Gu. Affective feature extraction for music emotion prediction. In *MediaEval*. Citeseer, 2015.
- [63] L. Lu, D. Liu, and H.-J. Zhang. Automatic mood detection and tracking of music audio signals. *IEEE Transactions on audio, speech, and language processing*, 14(1):5–18, 2005.
- [64] J. MacQueen et al. Some methods for classification and analysis of multivariate observations. In *Proceedings of the fifth Berkeley symposium on mathematical statistics and probability*, volume 1, pages 281–297. Oakland, CA, USA, 1967.
- [65] K. Markov and T. Matsui. Dynamic Music Emotion Recognition Using State-Space Models. Technical report, University of Aizu, MediaEval 2014 Workshop, 2014.
- [66] K. Markov and T. Matsui. Music Genre and Emotion Recognition Using Gaussian Processes. *IEEE Access*, 2:688–697, 2014.
- [67] S. McAdams and K. Siedenburg. Perception and cognition of musical timbre1.

- [68] B. McFee, C. Raffel, D. Liang, D. P. Ellis, M. McVicar, E. Battenberg, and O. Nieto. *librosa: Audio and music signal analysis in python*. In *Proceedings of the 14th python in science conference*, volume 8, pages 18–25. Citeseer, 2015.
- [69] L. McInnes, J. Healy, and J. Melville. Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03426*, 2018.
- [70] C. McKay. Emotion and music: Inherent responses and the importance of empirical cross-cultural research.
- [71] O. C. Meyers. *A mood-based music classification and exploration system*. PhD thesis, Massachusetts institute of technology, 2007.
- [72] N. Mor, L. Wolf, A. Polyak, and Y. Taigman. A universal music translation network. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.07848*, 2018.
- [73] S. T. Mueller. Distance, similarity, and multidimensional scaling. <https://pages.mtu.edu/~shanem/psy5220/daily/Day16/MDS.html#similarity-versus-distance>. 2021-03-21.
- [74] K. Nagesh Singh Chauhan. DbSCAN clustering algorithm in machine learning. <https://www.kdnuggets.com/2020/04/dbscan-clustering-algorithm-machine-learning.html>. April 4, 2022.
- [75] U. Nam. Special area exam part ii. <https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~unjung/AIR/areaExam.pdf>. April 28, 2001.
- [76] G. Ozcan, C. Isikhan, and A. Alpkocak. Melody extraction on midi music files. In *Seventh IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia (ISM'05)*, pages 8–pp. Ieee, 2005.
- [77] R. Panda, R. Malheiro, and R. P. Paiva. Novel audio features for music emotion recognition. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 11(4):614–626, 2018.

- [78] R. Panda and R. P. Paiva. Automatic creation of mood playlists in the thayer plane: A methodology and a comparative study. In *8th Sound and Music Computing Conference (SMC2011)*, 2011.
- [79] R. Panda and R. P. Paiva. Music emotion classification: Dataset acquisition and comparative analysis. In *15th International Conference on Digital Audio Effects-DAFx 2012*, 2012.
- [80] R. Panda, B. Rocha, and R. P. Paiva. Dimensional music emotion recognition: Combining standard and melodic audio features. In *10th International Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research-CMMR 2013*, pages 583–593, 2013.
- [81] B. G. Patra, P. Maitra, D. Das, S. Bandyopadhyay, et al. Mediaeval 2015: Music emotion recognition based on feed-forward neural network. In *MediaEval*, 2015.
- [82] R. W. Picard and J. Klein. Computers that recognise and respond to user emotion: theoretical and practical implications. *Interacting with computers*, 14(2):141–169, 2002.
- [83] P. Raguraman, R. Mohan, and M. Vijayan. Librosa based assessment tool for music information retrieval systems. In *2019 IEEE Conference on Multimedia Information Processing and Retrieval (MIPR)*, pages 109–114. IEEE, 2019.
- [84] M. G. Rigg. The mood effects of music: A comparison of data from four investigators. *The journal of psychology*, 58(2):427–438, 1964.
- [85] M. Ringnér. What is principal component analysis? *Nature biotechnology*, 26(3):303–304, 2008.
- [86] J. A. Russell. A circumplex model of affect. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 39(6):1161, 1980.
- [87] M. Saeed. Guide to multidimensional scaling in python with scikit-learn. <https://stackabuse.com/guide-to-multidimensional-scaling-in-python-with-scikit-learn/>.

- [88] E. Schubert. Update of the hevner adjective checklist. *Perceptual and motor skills*, 96(3_suppl):1117–1122, 2003.
- [89] B. Schuller, S. Steidl, A. Batliner, A. Vinciarelli, K. Scherer, F. Ringeval, M. Chetouani, F. Weninger, F. Eyben, E. Marchi, et al. The interspeech 2013 computational paralinguistics challenge: Social signals, conflict, emotion, autism. In *Proceedings INTERSPEECH 2013, 14th Annual Conference of the International Speech Communication Association, Lyon, France*, 2013.
- [90] F. Sebastiani. Machine learning in automated text categorization. *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)*, 34(1):1–47, 2002.
- [91] M. Soleymani, A. Aljanaki, and Y. Yang. Deam: Mediaeval database for emotional analysis in music, 2016.
- [92] J. Starmer. Statquest: t-sne, clearly explained. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NEaUSP4YerM>. Mar 31, 2022.
- [93] H. C. Test. Ch 10 optics. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CV0mWaHOTA8>. Jan 12, 2021.
- [94] K. Thimm and B. Fischer. Emotional responses to music: Influence of psychoacoustical features. In *National Conferences on Undergraduate Research*, 2003.
- [95] L. Van der Maaten and G. Hinton. Visualizing data using t-sne. *Journal of machine learning research*, 9(11), 2008.
- [96] M. Van Zaanen and P. Kanters. Automatic mood classification using tf* idf based on lyrics. In *ISMIR*, volume 9, pages 75–80, 2010.
- [97] J.-C. Wang, Y.-H. Yang, K. Chang, H.-M. Wang, and S.-K. Jeng. Exploring the relationship between categorical and dimensional emotion semantics of music. In *Proceedings of the second international ACM workshop on Music information retrieval with user-centered and multimodal strategies*, pages 63–68, 2012.

- [98] F. Weninger, F. Eyben, and B. Schuller. The tum approach to the mediaeval music emotion task using generic affective audio features. In *Proceedings MediaEval 2013 Workshop, Barcelona, Spain, 2013*.
- [99] Wikipedia. Opensmile. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OpenSMILE>.
- [100] Wikipedia. Spectral centroid. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Spectral_centroid. May 26, 2022.
- [101] S. with Josh Starmer. Clustering with dbscan, clearly explained!!! <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RDZUdRSD0ok>. Jan 10, 2022.
- [102] A. C. B. with Letitia. Umap explained | the best dimensionality reduction? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6BP181wGGP8>. Feb 18, 2021.
- [103] M. Xu, X. Li, H. Xianyu, J. Tian, F. Meng, and W. Chen. Multi-scale Approaches to the MediaEval 2015 "Emotion in Music" Task. Technical report, Tsinghua University, MediaEval 2015 Workshop, 2015.
- [104] W. Yang, K. Cai, B. Wu, Y. Wang, X. Chen, D. Yang, and A. Horner. Beatsens' Solution for MediaEval 2014 Emotion in Music Task. Technical report, Peking University, MediaEval 2014 Workshop, 2014.
- [105] Y.-H. Yang and H. H. Chen. Machine recognition of music emotion: A review. *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology (TIST)*, 3(3):1–30, 2012.
- [106] Y.-H. Yang, Y.-C. Lin, H.-T. Cheng, I.-B. Liao, Y.-C. Ho, and H. H. Chen. Toward multi-modal music emotion classification. In *Pacific-Rim Conference on Multimedia*, pages 70–79. Springer, 2008.
- [107] Yufeng. Understanding optics and implementation with python. <https://zhuanlan.zhihu.com/p/563066804>. 2022-09-09.
- [108] 喝CV的咖啡. t-sne/三分钟动画/史上最简单版本. https://www.bilibili.com/video/BV1va411m74T/?spm_id_from=333.337.search-card.all.click&vd_source=2ee939e950cf9760e73dc016c97105c9.

- [109] 大白兔黑又黑. 机器学习笔记 (十一) 聚类算法optics原理和实践. <https://blog.csdn.net/haveanybody/article/details/113782209>. 2021-02-24.
- [110] 生信修炼手册. Optics聚类算法详解. https://blog.csdn.net/weixin_43569478/article/details/115019317. 2021-03-19.
- [111] 皮卡丘的情绪. Dbscan详解. https://blog.csdn.net/hansome_hong/article/details/107596543. 2023-07-05.